

CREATING LEVERAGE TO
ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

CO-DESIGNING APPROACHES TO REDUCE BIODIVERSITY IMPACTS OF BIOMASS TRADE

A CLEVER Innovation Action Pool

CITATION AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This report identifies promising public and private sector governance innovations to reduce biodiversity impacts from non-food biomass supply chains including commodities like soy, timber, wood pulp and aquaculture products.

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Cover photo: Kapok Tree in Congo Basin. Credit: Juan Manuel Vargas.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
2. INTRODUCTION	12
3. OBJECTIVES	14
4. METHODS	16
4.1. Drawing on CLEVER literature	17
4.2. Synthesis and categorization	19
4.3. Expert deep-dive selection and analysis	20
5. ACTIONS TO REDUCE BIODIVERSITY IMPACTS OF TRADE	22
6. DEEP DIVES OF PRIORITIZED APPROACHES FOR ACTION	30
6.1. Targeted strategies through the lens of land tenure	32
6.2. Impact of standard-like non-tariff measures on biodiversity	39
6.3. Supply chain due diligence policies	43
6.4. Harnessing government procurement to incentivize positive biodiversity actions	47
6.5. Participatory approach to forest governance	52
6.6. Ecological taxes and other fiscal incentives	56
6.7. Sustainability certifications: An example from the aquaculture sector	60
6.8. Strengthening forest governance through independent monitoring	64
6.9. Industry-wide agreements: An example from the Amazon	70
6.10. Scaling finance for nature with blended finance structures	74
6.11. Payments for environmental services	80
6.12. Vertical and horizontal policy integration	84
7. CONCLUSIONS	90
8. REFERENCES	94

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Credit: Carl Cerstrand on Unsplash.

Global supply chains for major commodities, including soy, timber and wood pulp, are placing escalating pressure on global ecosystems and biodiversity.

Current projections indicate that commodity-driven supply chains will cause up to one quarter of all projected species extinctions and approximately one third of future forest loss. These ecological impacts directly threaten communities, businesses and governments dependent on healthy natural systems.¹

Regulatory efforts in high-income consumer markets are currently inadequate for the escalating biodiversity crisis.

Current measures fall short in addressing the speed and magnitude of environmental degradation driven by global commodity trade. This report identifies promising governance innovations that can be scaled up to create sustainable supply chains – ones that protect biodiversity while ensuring fair and sustainable production practices. We call this the CLEVER Innovation Action Pool.^{2,3,4} Its main target includes state actors and business associations in both producing (exporting) and consuming (importing) countries.

Stakeholders consistently emphasized that innovation needed to effect transformation of supply chains should focus on ambitious incremental progress and participatory design.

This recurring insight informed the structure of this toolkit and underpins its recommendations.

This work was grounded in co-design, ensuring input from broad and diverse stakeholder groups. This included regional co-design workshops in Yaoundé, Cameroon and Libreville, Gabon, complemented by internal expert workshops conducted by UNEP-WCMC and CLEVER partners. A comprehensive review of relevant literature and project outputs was carried out, then complemented by insights from over 200 regional interviews conducted by CLEVER in Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon.

This rigorous process identified 58 actionable innovations, organized within 15 categories.

These encompass financial instruments, fiscal policy, business governance, certification systems, community participation, anti-corruption measures, partnership models, regulatory frameworks, adaptive monitoring, research initiatives, circular economy practices, capacity-building strategies, and integrated implementation approaches. Table 1 – Illustrative Approaches provides a summary of these categories and their contents.

CLEVER Annual Meeting in Vienna (Austria), November 2023. Credit: Rosa Castañeda.

TABLE 1**CATEGORIES FOR MAPPED APPROACHES AND ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES**

CATEGORY	ILLUSTRATIVE APPROACHES
Financial Instruments & Access	Blended finance vehicles payments for ecosystem services, green bonds, microcredit for smallholders
Taxation & Fiscal Instruments	Ecological taxes, bonus-malus incentives, tax reform for conservation
Business Governance	Benefit corporations, cooperative ownership, value-sharing contracts
Certification & Standards	Dual-track certification, national schemes, sector roundtables
Community Participation	Co-developed governance, community forest management, participatory mapping
Consumer Action & Demand-Side	Behaviour changes campaigns, import thresholds, voluntary import moratoriums
Anti-Corruption & Transparency	Independent forest monitoring, open data platforms, satellite verification
Partnerships & Collective Action	Industry-wide binding agreements, landscape partnerships, multi-stakeholder coalitions
State Regulation (Hard Law)	Supply chain due diligence, biodiversity clauses in trade agreements, government procurement policies
State Soft Law & Subsidy Reform	Sustainability guidelines for banks, subsidy redirection, voluntary codes
Monitoring & Adaptive Management	Digital monitoring systems, geo-referenced land tracking, joint evaluation initiatives
Research & Knowledge Systems	Species management R&D, knowledge-sharing platforms, policy review cycles
Sector Efficiency & Circular Economy	Circular models for forest products, innovative by-product recovery
Capacity-Building & Transition	Farmer transition support, technical training for SMEs, institutional readiness grants
Cross-Cutting Implementation	Jurisdictional strategies (e.g. PCI-Mato Grosso), rights-based prioritization, policy integration

From this broader set, 12 approaches were selected for deeper analysis, prioritizing those with strong strategic relevance and based on a convenience sample given project team expertise.

The selection was not exhaustive, but aimed to generate focused, credible insights on approaches with high transformative potential. These deep dives also serve to complement and expand on the range of perspectives and priorities collected from stakeholders. Some (i) key lessons, (ii) examples of incremental innovations, and (iii) expected outcomes from the 12 prioritized approaches are summarized in Table 2 – Expected Outcomes.

KEY FINDINGS AND CROSS-CUTTING LESSONS FROM THIS WORK INCLUDE:

1 Incremental and participatory improvement is critical. Effective solutions leverage existing initiatives, actively involving local stakeholders, especially women, youth and Indigenous Peoples.

2 Transparency and digital monitoring strengthen accountability. Reliable and accessible information systems enhance stakeholder confidence and enforcement effectiveness.

3 Government procurement processes at the state level can drive sustainability. Embedding robust environmental and social criteria into government procurement policies shifts incentives, supports supplier capacity, and helps mitigate enforcement and inclusion risks.

4 Tailored access to finance is essential. Financial instruments, such as blended finance, are most effective when specifically structured to meet the realities and constraints faced by smallholders, local communities, Indigenous Peoples and SMEs.

5 Systemic change demands integrated action and harmonization across sectors and levels of governance. This is essential because fragmented, siloed policies can undermine impact and lead to conflicting objectives. Harmonization strategies can include formal cross-ministerial taskforces, joint policy mapping and shared knowledge platforms to enable coordinated delivery, as demonstrated in country case studies.

6 Scaling and adapting these 12 approaches can deliver measurable reductions in deforestation, increase equitable benefit-sharing, improve supplier inclusion, and build more resilient local economies.

TABLE 2

SUMMARY OF THE KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM THE 12 DEEP DIVES IN THE INNOVATION ACTION POOL

APPROACH	KEY LESSONS & CHALLENGES	INCREMENTAL INNOVATIONS (ACTORS & ACTIONS)	EXPECTED OUTCOMES
1 Targeted strategies through the lens of land tenure	Secure, inclusive tenure is essential; unclear rights cause exclusion/conflict, worsened by political and data barriers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lead spatial mapping that integrates land tenure and biodiversity data; reform and update land registries. • Co-design PES schemes that reflect local tenure; participate in registry reforms. 	Improved targeting of conservation interventions, greater equity in benefit sharing, increased legitimacy and effectiveness of biodiversity governance.
2 Impact of standard-like non-tariff measures on biodiversity (NTMs)	High compliance costs and fragmented standards burden smallholders; cross-country recognition can help but is complex.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiate mutual recognition of standards, streamline regulatory requirements. • Provide technical assistance and support platforms to producers. • Build capacity and facilitate adoption among smallholders. 	Greater market access with lower compliance barriers, increased sustainability of production practices, improved inclusion of small producers.
3 Supply chain due diligence policies	Effective due diligence needs clear coverage, strong enforcement, and real support for small producers; gaps remain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set and enforce clear due diligence regulations. • Build digital traceability systems and expand due diligence to SMEs. • Support IT system development. • Deliver capacity-building to small producers. 	Increased accountability and improved risk management throughout the supply chain, fairer burden-sharing, and more resilient supplier networks.
4 Harnessing government procurement	Procurement only drives change if criteria are robust, verification is strong, and local suppliers get support.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embed biodiversity criteria in procurement processes. • Train and verify suppliers. • Provide supplier support and sustainability consulting. 	Stronger sustainable markets, increased adoption of best practices, and improved supplier inclusion in public procurement.
5 Participatory approach to forest governance	True results depend on broad participation, power-sharing, and trust-building; logistical/cultural barriers persist.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate participatory mapping and policy co-design. • Lead on-the-ground governance and share local knowledge. • Coordinate capacity building and continuous stakeholder engagement. 	Enhanced legitimacy, improved policy effectiveness, and more sustainable, equitable forest governance.
6 Ecological taxes and fiscal incentives	Incentives must be granular and transparent; without consultation, smallholders risk extra burdens.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design and administer reward-penalty (“bonus-malus”) systems. • Adjust practices to maximize incentives. • Monitor impacts and advocate for equitable design. 	Improved conservation finance, greater adoption of sustainable practices, and reduced unintended impacts on smallholders.
7 Sustainability certifications	Inclusion and scalability require dual track/national certification and targeted support for smallholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop modular schemes and provide digital verification. • Facilitate group certification and training. • Align procurement with certification standards. 	Broader participation in certification, improved traceability, and better market rewards for sustainable producers.
8 Independent monitoring to strengthen forest governance	Monitoring needs legal backing, institutional support, and open data; impact is limited otherwise.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize national observer networks and train community monitors. • Develop and maintain digital reporting tools. • Provide legal framework and facilitate access to data. 	Improved enforcement, reduced corruption, and stronger accountability in forest governance.
9 Industry-wide binding agreements	Sectoral agreements only work with broad participation and tough enforcement; risk of leakage if partial.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate agreement and ensure broad buy-in. • Commit and comply with sector standards. • Monitor adherence and report violations. • Support scaling to new regions or commodities. 	Systemic sectoral change, reduced deforestation, and increased accountability among all supply chain actors.
10 Scaling finance for nature with blended finance structures	Blended finance can mobilize capital but depends on quality projects and local capacity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structure blended finance vehicles. • Build local pipeline of projects and provide technical assistance. • Offer risk guarantees. 	Greater scale and diversity of sustainable investments, stronger project pipelines, and increased access to finance for local actors.
11 Payments for environmental services (PES)	PES effectiveness relies on tailored design, market integration, tenure security, and strong monitoring.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-design PES schemes with landholders, including • Integrate digital monitoring, link PES to credit access. • Participate in co-design, contract negotiation and delivery. 	Greater adoption of PES, improved stewardship of natural resources, and fairer benefit-sharing with local communities.
12 Vertical and horizontal policy integration	Policy integration boosts effectiveness, but is hampered by silos, lack of leadership, and poor coordination.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish cross-sectoral taskforces, conduct policy mapping, enable knowledge platforms. • Support iterative review and capacity building. 	More coherent, impactful, and sustainable policy implementation across scales and sectors.

 Government: National Policymakers/Regulators

 Government: Agencies/Implementers

 Intergovernmental/International Policymakers

 Civil Society & NGOs

 LCs and IPs

 Private Sector: Companies

 Private Sector: Business Associations

 Certification Bodies

 Technical & IT Providers

 Producer Organizations

 Financial Institutions & Investors

Although this work began with a science-driven focus on biodiversity, stakeholder input during co-design underscored that the political economy shaping supply chains cannot be ignored. Land tenure,⁵ smallholder and community inclusion,⁶ corruption and transparency,⁷ state action and harmonized policies⁸ and targeted capacity building⁹ surfaced as indispensable leverage points for transformative outcomes: findings that directly reinforce the already widely recognized conclusion that governance solutions only succeed when they confront these interconnected challenges and embed local voices at every stage.^{5,10}

Immediate, coordinated action is essential. Nature's rapid decline demands urgent, cross-sector responses across government, business, civil society and finance.¹¹

Achieving systemic change in global commodity supply chains will require stakeholders from all sectors to engage actively and contribute to ambitious targets, building on the heightened momentum for transformation.¹² Cross-sector collaboration is crucial to halt commodity-driven deforestation and biodiversity loss.¹²

Robust evidence demonstrates that strategies like securing land-tenure rights for IPs and LCs through participatory approaches directly reduces deforestation and underpins biodiversity gains, as shown in Brazil.^{5,13} Sector-wide agreements, such as Brazil's Amazon Soy Moratorium, have delivered measurable declines in deforestation.^{14,15} This work lays out more evidence-based approaches and incremental innovations that can also improve nature, social, and economic outcomes.

The UN Secretary-General warns that humanity's "appetite for unchecked and unequal economic growth has become a weapon of mass extinction," bringing the world to a "code red for humanity" that requires transformative action now.¹⁶ To enhance action on the ground, and increase the chances for sustainability strategies to succeed, stakeholders are urged to scale up efforts, integrate scientific evidence into decision-making, and strengthen joint action.¹⁷

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2. INTRODUCTION

Global supply chains are a key point of intersection between international trade dynamics and biodiversity conservation, and a critical driver of changes in the state of both land cover and livelihoods. Recent analyses estimate that agricultural expansion drives 6.4 to 8.8 million hectares of tropical deforestation annually, releasing around 2.6 gigatonnes of CO₂ each year, equivalent to or exceeding those from domestic agriculture in many consuming countries (Pendrill et al. 2019a; Pendrill et al. 2019b; Pendrill et al. 2022). Between 25 per cent and nearly 40 per cent of this deforestation and associated emissions are linked to international trade in commodities such as beef, soy and oil palm (Pendrill et al. 2019b; Pendrill et al. 2022).

This dynamic is well illustrated by the expansion of agricultural and forestry activities to meet global demand, which causes deforestation, habitat loss and species decline, often in biodiversity-rich regions of the Global South where many commodity production systems are located (Chaudhary et al. 2016; Green et al. 2019; Pendrill et al. 2019a). A substantial proportion of exports of key commodities such as soy and timber from these regions is destined for international markets in Europe, China and other high-income economies, creating a geographical disconnect between production landscapes and some centres of consumption (Pendrill et al. 2019b; Reis et al. 2020). This situation results in governance challenges that require innovative approaches to ensure sustainable supply chains and protect biodiversity (Arto et al. 2022; Cabernard et al. 2024).

Current regulatory frameworks and market mechanisms have shown limited effectiveness in addressing these telecoupled¹ impacts at the scale and speed required (Lambin et al. 2018; Kehoe et al. 2020). The speed and magnitude of biodiversity loss linked to global trade, maintained by continuing demand, calls for more transformative governance approaches that can create systemic change rather than for incremental improvements (Leventon et al. 2021; Pascual et al. 2022).

CLEVER is a research project that works to inform EU-level policymaking around global trade by providing scientifically informed recommendations to achieve positive biodiversity outcomes. Recognizing the urgent need for more effective and transformative approaches to governing the biodiversity impacts of trade, the project looks for opportunities to improve the sustainability of trade policies in the EU and trade partner countries. It seeks to develop new approaches to governance and interventions based on better supply chain information.

¹ Telecoupling refers to how trade and supply chains link distant regions, causing environmental and social impacts far from where consumption occurs.

3.OBJECTIVES

Squirrel monkey,
Isla de los Micos,
Colombia.

The objective of the CLEVER Innovation Action Pool is to document and characterize public policies and private sector governance arrangements that can enable more sustainable value chains and trade. Specifically, it maps approaches to reducing deforestation and biodiversity impacts from non-food biomass production and trade (focusing on soy, timber, wood pulp and fishmeal). These ideas come from a variety of consultations with stakeholders and researchers.

The project focuses on trade flows between the EU and Brazil and the EU and Central Africa. However, the Innovation Action Pool also presents "innovative solutions" that have proven useful in other parts of the world and that could be scaled up in appropriate locations.

The target audience of the Innovation Action Pool includes state actors and business associations in both producing (exporting) and consuming (importing) countries. It may also be of interest to researchers in the fields of trade, policy and sustainability, as well as non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and stakeholders who actively engaged in the development of the project outputs. CLEVER co-design partners were identified in internal mapping discussions as wide-reaching groups with high leverage and interest in transforming supply chains towards sustainable arrangements for nature.

Shipments in Douala's Docks.
Credit: Juan Manuel Vargas.

4. METHODS

To develop the Innovation Action Pool, we employed a co-design methodology (Box 1). Through co-design, we sought to capture diverse stakeholder perspectives and leverage expert knowledge to identify and characterize governance approaches for biodiversity-positive trade in the focus commodities. The methodology combined bottom-up stakeholder input with top-down expert analysis, striking a balance between real-world relevance and scientific detail.

BOX 1 / CO-DESIGN IN CONTEXT

Traditional supply chain governance often does not include deliberative democracy criteria like inclusiveness and consequentiality (Schouten et al. 2012). Therefore, we used a co-design approach to develop the Innovation Action Pool, which helps to facilitate participatory design-thinking processes and practical tools for innovation (Blomkamp 2018). In policymaking, these can support the generation of validated results relevant for stakeholders and decision makers (Pulido-Velazquez et al. 2023). In addition, we aimed to ensure governance innovations reflected diverse perspectives and addressed systemic exclusions. To support this aim, we actively prioritized the representation and inclusion of all sectors of stakeholders in the supply chains, as well as marginalized voices when possible. The latter triggered specific efforts to enable women and youth groups’ participation, given the broadly male-dominated stakeholder representation at producer and trader levels in supply chains (Nakazibwe and Pelupessy 2014).

4.1. DRAWING ON CLEVER LITERATURE

The first step was to build an initial list of innovative governance approaches drawing from CLEVER research, including the following CLEVER publications (see Table 3).

TABLE 3

CLEVER RESEARCH USED AS A STARTING POINT

PUBLICATION TITLE	AUTHORS
Literature Review and Conceptual Framework on Mechanisms of How Biomass Trade Affects Biodiversity as Input	(Pacheco and Börner 2023)
Map of Public and Private Policies and Governance Mechanisms	(Berning et al. 2023)
Theories of Change and Influence Pathways of Forest Related Public and Private Regulations	(Berning et al. 2024)
Assessing horizontal and vertical policy and regulatory governance (in) coherence	(Ziegert et al. 2024)
Behavioural responses to value chain related policies and governance initiatives	(Cramm et al. 2024)
Actor-Specific Leverage Points for Transformative Change	(Cramm et al. 2025)

4.1.1. SCOPING AND STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

Preliminary scoping began at the workshop titled "[Toward compliance with the EU Deforestation Regulation: Criteria, Tools, and Open Questions](#)" in November 2023. This workshop engaged German and EU companies and researchers to understand private sector approaches to emerging regulations such as the European Union's Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR)². The workshop provided foundational insights into business perspectives on supply chain responses and governance innovations.

4.1.2. SYSTEMATIC STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Targeted stakeholder engagement events aimed for broad stakeholder input into the Innovation Action Pool (listed in chronological order):

- **Stakeholder reference group interviews:** We held semi-structured interviews with members of the CLEVER project's [stakeholder reference group](#). The stakeholder reference group is a set of representatives from the policy sector, business, certification bodies and civil society initiatives in areas within the project's geographic scope. The group was established to help refine assumptions, hypotheses and modelling scenarios for the CLEVER project and to ensure the relevance, credibility and legitimacy of the project's outcomes. Additionally, we conducted a targeted consultation with a local gender and youth advocate in the Congo Basin to inform the design of the workshops. While recognizing that a single consultation does not capture the full diversity of perspectives, this input contributed to dedicating a specific category in the mapping exercises for issues affecting women and young people, and to prioritizing gender balance in participant selection. The same advocate also participated in one of the regional workshops, providing further insights during the discussions.
- **Regional stakeholder interviews:** Around 200 interviews took place between October 2023 and April 2024 with stakeholders across Brazil, Cameroon and Gabon to gather diverse perspectives on supply chain governance and contextual priorities in each region. While these interviews primarily informed Deliverable 5.1: "[Behavioural responses to value chain related policies and governance initiatives](#)", and Deliverable 5.2: "[Qualitative assessment of leakage and other spillover potentials in selected value chains](#)", insights from them also contributed to the evidence base underpinning this report.
- **Internal expert workshops:** CLEVER partners contributed directly through a systematic survey, with results compiled in CLEVER's internal Milestone 21. Further, a series of internal workshops were held with UNEP-WCMC experts representing diverse disciplinary backgrounds including forest policy, international trade, social science, gender and human rights, green finance and environmental economics. These workshops initially mapped governance approaches and later refined stakeholder inputs.
- **Regional co-design workshops:** Two co-design workshops were delivered in October 2024 in Central Africa in Yaoundé, Cameroon and Libreville, Gabon. These workshops had 31 and 15 participants respectively. The goal of these workshops was to ensure that local context and stakeholder priorities were captured. These events included participants from businesses, operators, academia, NGOs, IPs and LCs, women and youth groups and government representatives. Participants worked collaboratively to suggest innovative governance approaches, map connections between them and identify potential synergies or conflicts. This exercise supported dialogue on aligning policies and resolving overlaps or tensions. This participatory process also served as a form of stakeholder validation, with particular emphasis on incorporating perspectives from producer regions in the Global South. The Central African workshops were specifically designed to counterbalance the bias towards consumer-country perspectives that is common in supply chain governance research, as highlighted by stakeholders.

² The European Union's [Regulation on Deforestation-free Products](#) requires that certain commodities placed on or exported from the EU market are deforestation-free.

4.2. SYNTHESIS AND CATEGORIZATION

A multi-phased approach was used to build on initial ideas and generate a thorough longlist of potential approaches:

- **Snowball sampling and database development:** All stakeholder engagement activities contributed to a growing list of innovative governance approaches built through snowballing (ie a cumulative process where participants recommend additional relevant contacts or ideas). Each activity highlighted additional approaches, which were systematically documented and cross-referenced to avoid duplication, while aiming to maintain the full variety of stakeholder-identified approaches.
- **Expert-led refinement:** Since time with stakeholders was limited, their initial inputs required additional research for verification and contextualization. An expert group at UNEP-WCMC helped to aggregate, clarify and develop stakeholder inputs into a list of verified policy approaches. This process involved:
 1. **Aggregation:** Combining similar approaches identified across different stakeholder groups.
 2. **Clarification:** Developing brief stakeholder insights into more detailed policy descriptions. In some cases, this meant taking a brief point made by a stakeholder and conducting research into what governance approaches have been successful in achieving what the stakeholder highlighted.
 3. **Conceptual development:** Ensuring each approach was grounded in the project's conceptual framework.
- **Multi-dimensional categorization:** The refined approaches were categorized considering features such as: (i) implementing actor type (ie whether approaches are primarily driven by state actors, private sector entities, civil society organizations or multi-stakeholder coalitions); (ii) area of work (eg finance, regulation, certification etc.); (iii) policy instrument type (ie the mechanism through which change is achieved, eg regulatory, market-based, voluntary, etc.); and (iv) trade relation to commodity, or whether they were on the demand or supply side of the supply chain.

The categorization exercise resulted in the broad categories of governance innovation approaches listed in Table 4:

TABLE 4

BROAD CATEGORIES FOR INNOVATION APPROACHES

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION
Financial Instruments and Access to Finance	Mechanisms that improve funding availability or create financial incentives for sustainable supply chain practices.
Taxation and Fiscal Instruments	Use of taxes, subsidies or fiscal reforms to discourage unsustainable practices or promote sustainable ones.
Business Governance and Corporate Structures	Internal company policies, codes of conduct and structural changes that promote accountability and sustainability.
Certification and Standards	Voluntary or mandatory schemes that set sustainability benchmarks for production, trade or sourcing.
Community Participation and Local Involvement	Approaches that actively engage local communities, Indigenous Peoples, women and youth.

Consumer Action and Demand-Side Measures	Initiatives that inform or influence consumers to drive market demand for sustainable or deforestation-free products.
Partnerships and Collective Action	Collaborative arrangements among stakeholders (eg public-private, multi-stakeholder) to align goals, coordinate efforts or share best practice.
State-Level Regulation and Hard Law	Binding national or subnational legal frameworks enforcing sustainability requirements.
State-Level Soft Law and Subsidy Reform	Non-binding policies, guidelines or subsidy adjustments that support sustainable supply chain transitions.
Monitoring and Adaptive Management	Systems for tracking outcomes and revising strategies over time based on performance and new evidence.
Research and Knowledge Systems	Scientific, technical or traditional knowledge generation and dissemination to inform governance and decision-making.
Sector Efficiency and Circular Economy	Innovations that reduce waste, increase resource-use efficiency or promote circular practices within commodity sectors.
Capacity-Building and Transition Support	Initiatives aimed at improving the skills, resources or institutional readiness of stakeholders to participate in sustainable governance.
Cross-Cutting Implementation Strategies	Tools or approaches that integrate multiple dimensions (eg legal, financial, social) to operationalize and scale governance innovations.

4.3. EXPERT DEEP-DIVE SELECTION AND ANALYSIS

From the comprehensive longlist, 12 approaches were selected for in-depth analysis according to their broad strategic relevance and a convenience sample based on availability of appropriate technical capacity. UNEP-WCMC and CLEVER experts were matched to specific approaches based on proven expertise. Researchers and practitioners with ample and demonstrated experience in their relevant policy domains were prioritized. Each expert conducted a comprehensive analysis of their assigned approach, (i) examining and defining it and its theory of change, and (ii) exploring evidence-based innovations that can improve its impact or enable its uptake.

Following stakeholder feedback, particularly from the co-design workshops in Cameroon and Gabon, the methodology deliberately shifted the innovation-focus toward innovative incremental improvements to existing policies and approaches, rather than novel or standalone interventions. Stakeholders emphasized the value of building on established systems and

institutional knowledge, highlighting that new initiatives are most effective when they connect with existing structures and priorities. Stakeholders expressed a preference for strengthening and adapting what is already in place, especially by making governance approaches more inclusive, context-aware and better aligned across governance levels and sectors.

Consequently, the Innovation Action Pool focuses on lessons that can be drawn from existing policies and on identifying opportunities to align and improve them. It applies concepts developed by Ziegert et al. (2024) to explore how layered and interacting governance mechanisms can be harmonized to achieve more effective and inclusive outcomes. In this framing, innovation is not defined by novelty alone, but by its ability to improve legitimacy, coherence and impact, particularly by creating space for more meaningful participation from stakeholders who have traditionally been underrepresented in governance processes. Taken together, this multi-phase, participatory methodology ensures that the Innovation Action Pool reflects both stakeholder priorities and expert analysis, offering a set of approaches that are both theoretically sound and practically feasible.

5. ACTIONS TO REDUCE BIODIVERSITY IMPACTS OF TRADE

Soybean farm.
Credit: Oticki
on Adobe
Stock.

This chapter presents 58 public and private sector governance approaches identified through stakeholder engagement and expert input across CLEVER's focus regions and commodities. The approaches are organized into 15 categories that range from financial instruments to cross-cutting implementation strategies.

The approaches listed in Table 5 cover a broad spectrum of implementing actors (ie public and private sectors, NGOs, academia). The approaches employ diverse pathways of influence, including rules-based regulation, market incentives, technology and local stakeholder involvement in participatory approaches, among others. While gathered in the contexts of EU-Brazil and EU-Central Africa trade relations, these instruments are, with varying levels of effectiveness and context-specific adjustments, scalable and applicable in broader and different settings.

The table should be read as a menu of options, providing a system-level overview of instruments that can be used to solve the range of obstacles to transitioning to a just and sustainable commodity trade system. The table lists approaches that could be mutually reinforcing if considered together, recognizing that addressing the impacts of trade on biodiversity and local people requires coordinated and harmonized interventions across multiple domains rather than reliance on a single policy or siloed solutions. Each approach requires careful consideration of local contexts, regulatory environments and stakeholder needs.

TABLE 5

FULL LIST OF APPROACHES IN THE INNOVATION ACTION POOL

FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS AND ACCESS TO FINANCE

Blended Finance and Financial Leverage

See Section 6.10: Scaling finance for nature with blended finance structures

Blended finance instruments like multi-actor vehicles that combine concessional and commercial capital to de-risk investments in biodiversity-positive supply chains

Policy-driven financial leverage, which can include public guarantees or first-loss tranches that crowd in private finance for forest-friendly production

Technical assistance grants and small grants paired with loans to build borrower capacity and reduce default risk

Concessional loans like below-market credit lines for producers adopting zero-deforestation practices

Payment for Environmental or Ecosystem Services (PES)

See Section 6.11: Payments for environmental services

Tailor-made and region-specific PES systems that meet local needs, incorporate best practices and build in innovation such as digital monitoring and verification

'PES-like' results-based carbon or biodiversity credit schemes where payments flow to local providers once verified

Linking PES to carbon-market revenue where carbon is an eligible ecosystem service, ensuring traceable benefit-sharing

Biodiversity Finance Systems

Carbon and biodiversity credit systems with equitable local benefit requirements and streamlined verification processes to maximize the value retained by communities

Coordinated "finance stacks" that blend ESG-screened investment, micro-credit, impact funds and earmarked grants (eg 1 % for the Planet) so instruments reinforce rather than duplicate one another

Outcome-Based Financial Instruments

Outcome-based financial instruments like the Responsible Commodities Fund and Violet that explicitly reward positive biodiversity impacts while penalizing harmful practices to create asymmetric incentives that go beyond risk mitigation to actively drive positive outcomes

Agricultural green bonds with metrics specifically designed for biodiversity improvement, fair labour practices and support for smallholder farmers, as well as sustainable supply chain transformation within appropriate timeframes

TAXATION AND FISCAL INSTRUMENTS

Ecological and Environmental Taxes

See Section 6.6: Ecological taxes and other fiscal incentives

Granular environmental taxation differentiating between production practices based on measurable biodiversity impacts

Progressive taxation on biodiversity-depleting goods (such as monocultures) with revenue transparently allocated to conservation efforts. Each externality has its own targeted fiscal instrument, with revenues earmarked to address the specific external cost

A levy per cubic meter of harvested timber that finances programs helping communities and companies transition away from deforestation-dependent activities

Tax Incentives and Preferential Treatment

Preferential tax treatment for certified sustainable commodities through reduced import duties, tax credits or accelerated depreciation for certified supply chain investments

Identify and redirect agricultural subsidies that incentivize biodiversity loss toward payments for ecosystem services and conservation-compatible production practices

Comprehensive Tax Reform

Implement comprehensive tax reforms that close avoidance loopholes and establish progressive wealth taxation specifically earmarked for ecological restoration and sustainable agricultural transition

BUSINESS GOVERNANCE AND CORPORATE STRUCTURES

Corporate Governance Innovation

Restructure corporate governance through benefit corporations, cooperative ownership or community-owned enterprises that build environmental accountability into their legal structure and decision-making processes. This innovation transforms business incentives by embedding biodiversity protection into ownership structures rather than treating it as external compliance

Contract Design and Supply Chain Governance

Use contract design as a governance tool to create more equitable value distribution throughout supply chains rather than relying solely on market forces or external regulation

Use structured contract negotiation frameworks that address power imbalances between buyers and producers through guaranteed pricing floors, profit-sharing mechanisms and risk distribution clauses to ensure equitable value distribution

Antitrust and Market Diversity

Agricultural antitrust policies designed to maintain market participant diversity to support production system diversity

CERTIFICATION AND STANDARDS

Sustainability Certification System Design

See Section 6.7: Sustainability certifications: An example from the aquaculture sector

Dual-track certification systems offering both individual and group pathways to accommodate different producer scales while maintaining verification integrity

Government-mandated national certification schemes developed to promote sustainable production, prioritizing inclusivity by making sustainability standards accessible to smallholder farmers, enforcing robust regulations on conservation and human rights

Industry-Wide Certification

Sector roundtables and collective certification approaches (eg RTRS, RSPO) that establish shared sustainability standards and verification systems for several businesses in particular commodities

Strategic alignment of private forest certification schemes with regulatory compliance requirements, reducing compliance costs while enhancing effectiveness of both approaches

COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION AND LOCAL INVOLVEMENT

Governance Mechanisms

Locally co-developed governance mechanisms that link site-level indicators (eg forest-cover change) to global biodiversity goals, ensuring metrics are feasible and decision-relevant

Participatory approaches

See Section 6.5: Participatory approach to forest governance

Implement participatory processes for forest governance including collaborative mapping exercises, inclusive drafting of forestry laws and application decrees with meaningful stakeholder input

Land Tenure and Community Forest Management

See Section 6.1: Targeted strategies through the lens of land tenure

Support the creation and sustainable management of community forests through technical assistance, secure tenure arrangements, market access programs and integration with broader conservation objectives

Improve the collection and detail of land tenure data. Incorporate land tenure considerations into biodiversity conservation and restoration policies to enhance their targeting and effectiveness

CONSUMER ACTION AND DEMAND-SIDE MEASURES

Behaviour Change and Consumption Limits

Develop sophisticated behaviour-change campaigns that make reduced consumption socially desirable by highlighting health, well-being and environmental benefits through targeted messaging and cultural influencers

Establish maximum per capita import thresholds for resource-intensive agricultural commodities in consumer countries to maintain consumption within ecological boundaries

Industry Voluntary Agreements

Implement industry-wide voluntary agreements to suspend commodity imports from high-risk regions until sustainability criteria are met

ANTI-CORRUPTION AND TRANSPARENCY

Independent Monitoring and Observation

See Section 6.8: Strengthening forest governance through independent monitoring

Strengthen forest governance through legally mandated independent external observation and platforms that combine satellite monitoring, field verification and public disclosure protocols. This approach innovates by institutionalizing transparency and third-party oversight using real-time data technologies to overcome enforcement limitations

PARTNERSHIPS AND COLLECTIVE ACTION

Industry-Wide Binding Agreements

See Section 6.9: Industry-wide agreements: An example from the Amazon

Create binding industry-wide agreements that prevent agricultural expansion into forested areas. This creates a shift from individual company pledges to collective industry accountability that creates market-wide transformation

Multi-Stakeholder Coalitions

Form alliances like Brazil's Climate, Forests and Agriculture Coalition that unite producers, companies, civil society and government to develop joint solutions and advocate for policy changes. These coalitions innovate by bridging traditional adversaries to build unexpected political momentum for sustainability reforms

Integrated Landscape Management

Implement integrated landscape management that coordinates actions across sectors, jurisdictions and stakeholders to balance agricultural production with conservation goals through collective decision-making structures

STATE-LEVEL REGULATION AND HARD LAW

Trade Agreement Provisions

See Section 6.3: Supply chain due diligence policies

Binding biodiversity protection clauses with enforcement mechanisms in trade agreements, measured by concrete metrics

Supply chain due diligence policies that require companies to verify commodity legality and sustainability, shifting responsibility upstream to importing companies rather than solely relying on producer country enforcement

Infrastructure and Market Development

Develop sustainable rural infrastructure to help create, shape and facilitate market access, with a focus on sustainable local livelihoods and resilient production systems. Consider integrated financial instruments and grants, community-driven participatory planning, climate-resilient and biodiversity sensitive infrastructure design, bundled infrastructure services, incentive-based funding and governance

Establish government-supported domestic processing facilities for sustainable wood and agricultural products to capture value locally while ensuring sustainability standards

Government Procurement

See Section 6.4: Harnessing government procurement to incentivize positive biodiversity actions

Government procurement policies requiring sustainability criteria for agricultural products, creating guaranteed markets for biodiversity-friendly commodities

Regulatory Clarity and Harmonization

Clarify and harmonize guidance frameworks to allow companies to confidently implement regulations and strategies

Non-tariff measures (NTMs)

See Section 6.2: Impact of standard-like non-tariff measures on biodiversity

Regulations that make market access conditional on meeting specific environmental, health or safety requirements. NTMs can restrict trade in commodities that cause biodiversity loss through their use or production

Strategic Enforcement

Environmental regulations that strategically leverage corporations' sensitivities about their reputations through public disclosure requirements and targeted enforcement in high-visibility areas

STATE-LEVEL SOFT LAW AND SUBSIDY REFORM

Subsidy Redirection

Shift government subsidies and technical assistance from export-oriented agribusiness toward small-scale farmers focused on local food production using diverse, ecologically-sound practices

Voluntary sustainability guidelines (soft law) for banks lending to agribusiness, paired with phased subsidy reform

MONITORING AND ADAPTIVE MANAGEMENT

Innovative Monitoring Systems

Employ innovative systems for monitoring policy effectiveness, such as Adaptive Management Frameworks (see USAID's CLA framework), Digital Monitoring Systems and Mobile Data Collection (see Kenya's use of mobile platforms to gather citizen feedback on service delivery), Behavioural Insights Teams ("Nudge Units" - see Mexico's use of BITs to fight corruption), Joint Evaluation Initiatives across jurisdictions (eg the Africa-Brazil Program on Social Development)

Implement monitoring systems with geo-referenced inventories that continually track changes in land use, resource extraction and compliance with sustainability measures

RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS

Species and Management Research

Research programs identifying management techniques for underutilized tree species paired with policy frameworks to support their sustainable commercialization

Periodic review cycles that update forest management standards as evidence and local needs evolve

Knowledge Sharing Mechanisms

Structured mechanisms for pre-competitive sharing of sustainability innovations across sector stakeholders, including open-source approaches and formal knowledge transfer protocols

SECTOR EFFICIENCY AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Circular Economy Models

Develop circular economy models for forest products that maximize timber utilization through cascading use principles, innovative processing technologies and byproduct recovery systems

CAPACITY BUILDING AND TRANSITION SUPPORT

Farmer Transition Support

Financial and technical support mechanisms specifically designed to carry farmers through temporary yield reductions during transitions to regenerative methods

CROSS-CUTTING IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES

Jurisdictional Approaches

Implement subnational public strategies like the Produce-Conserve-Include (PCI) in Mato Grosso that coordinate actions across an entire jurisdiction rather than individual supply chains

Rights-Based Prioritization

Prioritizing rights-based objectives over market mechanisms when conflicts arise (eg implementing a temporary pause on carbon markets to address fundamental rights concerns when they arise)

Policy Integration

See Section 6.12: Vertical and horizontal policy integration

Vertically and horizontally integrating sustainable trade policies across local, national and international levels to eliminate contradictions and create reinforcing effects

6. DEEP DIVES OF PRIORITIZED APPROACHES FOR ACTION

Capybara. Credit: Melisa on Adobe Stock.

Twelve approaches, derived from the longlist presented in Chapter 5, were selected for in-depth analysis, or deep dives. These are listed in Table 6. The analysis in this chapter is structured to offer both conceptual understanding and practical insights for implementation. It draws from existing literature and emerging research on innovative approaches to sustainability governance. Each section in this chapter aims to answer two main questions:

- i. What is the theory of change of the approach?
- ii. What scientific and empirical evidence is there of its application, or what lessons can be learned for innovation?

TABLE 6

APPROACHES PRIORITIZED FOR IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS (CHAPTER 6)

SECTION	APPROACH	BROADER CATEGORY
6.1	Targeted strategies through the lens of land tenure	Cross-cutting implementation strategies
6.2	Impact of standard-like non-tariff measures on biodiversity	State-level regulation and hard law
6.3	Supply chain due diligence policies	State-level regulation and hard law
6.4	Government procurement's role in incentivizing positive biodiversity actions	State-level regulation and hard law
6.5	Participatory approach to forest governance	Community participation and local involvement
6.6	Ecological taxes and other fiscal incentives	Taxation and fiscal instruments
6.7	Sustainability certifications	Certification and standards
6.8	Independent monitoring to strengthen forest governance	Anti-corruption and transparency
6.9	Industry-wide binding agreements	Partnerships and collective action
6.10	Blended finance and Financial Leverage	Financial instruments and access to finance
6.11	Payments for environmental services	Financial instruments and access to finance
6.12	Vertical and horizontal policy integration	Cross-cutting implementation strategies

The deep dives showcase different impact pathways

The deep dives highlight how attempts to control impacts on biodiversity conservation can be optimized and harmonized (eg by aligning standard-like non-tariff measures with biodiversity in Section 6.2; by Harnessing government procurement to incentivize positive biodiversity actions in Section 6.4; and by ensuring coordinated policy frameworks through Vertical and horizontal policy integration in Section 6.12).

In addition, the deep dives provide suggestions and examples of how to improve, augment and scale up actions through the use of new technologies (eg mobile applications enabling community monitors to send real time alerts about illegal activities in Section 6.8); spatial data and mapping (eg integrating improved biodiversity mapping and spatially explicit land tenure to inform tenure-sensitive biodiversity policies and governance mechanisms in Section 6.1); use of satellite data and property-level information to identify possible violations of the Amazon Soy moratorium in Section 6.9); and novel analysis techniques (eg measuring the effects of sustainability certification using high-resolution imagery to identify comparison sites in Section 6.7).

The approaches include innovative examples of project co-design (eg NGOs developing tools with indigenous monitors to investigate deforestation alerts in the Peruvian Amazon in Section 6.8); and application of innovative solutions to new contexts (eg applying the “bonus-malus” mechanism to ecotaxes, to incentivize more sustainable forestry practices in Section 6.6).

Development of partnerships and networks (eg national networks of monitoring organizations to coordinate roles and adopt common methodologies in Section 6.9, partnerships enabling investors to collaborate and converge on best-practice in Section 6.10) is also a recurring theme in the approaches.

The approaches address different leverage points along supply chains

In addition to describing an instrument, the 12 deep dives aim to demonstrate how the approaches operate on different leverage points along the supply chain, acting on aspects including production practices and land use (eg fiscal incentives for sustainable forestry in Section 6.6, sustainability certification in Section 6.7, payments for environmental services in Section 6.11); forest governance (eg public participation in environmental lawmaking in Section 6.5, independent forest monitoring and community vigilance in Section 6.8); markets (eg non-tariff measures in Section 6.2); sourcing practices (mandatory due diligence in Section 6.3, public procurement policies in Section 6.4, industry-wide agreements in Section 6.9); and investment decisions (eg blended finance in Section 6.10). While these intervention points are not structured according to the leverage points defined in the CLEVER deliverable [Actor-Specific Leverage Points for Transformative Change](#), many of the same challenges and opportunities identified there are addressed through the IAP's focus areas (Cramm et al. 2025).

6.1. TARGETED STRATEGIES THROUGH THE LENS OF LAND TENURE

Understanding land tenure systems (who owns or controls land and under what conditions) is fundamental to effective biodiversity conservation policy design and implementation. Land tenure categories include private lands, public lands, and communal or traditional lands. Approximately 11 per cent of land is legally owned by Indigenous Peoples and local communities, with 7 per cent designated for such communities. On the other hand, large private landowners play a decisive role, making them crucial conservation targets. Land tenure directly restricts land-use decision-making. For example, financial instruments like

payments for environmental services require formalized land ownership, while community participation works best on indigenous or communally held lands. Areas of innovation in land tenure include incorporating Indigenous Peoples and local communities when defining priority conservation areas, developing spatially explicit land tenure data sensitive to vulnerable groups' needs, and recognizing that mapping enables more effective and targeted biodiversity policies.

6.1.1. TARGETING INSTRUMENTS BASED ON PREDOMINANT LAND TENURE

Understanding land tenure systems – who owns or controls land and under what conditions – is fundamental to the effective design and implementation of many policies and governance mechanisms. Therefore, this section treats land tenure as a consideration that cuts across policy approaches and instruments rather than as a standalone policy approach. This section examines how incorporating land tenure considerations can enhance the targeting and effectiveness of biodiversity conservation policies.

Mitigating the negative impacts of trade on biodiversity requires accurately targeted policies and other governance mechanisms. Such targeting depends on two key components: first, identifying areas of threatened or high conservation-value biodiversity (Oliveira 2024a; Oliveira 2024b; Oliveira and Pacheco 2024), and second, understanding who owns or controls the land associated with this biodiversity and how it is (or is not) governed. Land tenure refers to the system of rules and norms that determine who owns or controls land and its associated resources. It also includes rules covering what activities are permitted including use, access, exclusion and management (Robinson et al. 2018). Land tenure systems have historically shaped socioecological dynamics and land-use patterns across the world. Typically, land tenure categories include:

- private lands (eg individually owned properties with formal title and legal rights, as recognized by the State government, to use, transfer or modify the land)
- public lands (eg protected areas (PAs), public forests, lands under no formal designation or other lands owned by the state)
- communal or other traditional lands (eg indigenous or other communally held lands which often have their own autonomous administration systems)

A recent estimate based on data from 73 countries covering 85 per cent of global land area indicates that at least 11 per cent of land is legally owned by Indigenous Peoples, Afro-descendant Peoples, and local communities and that a further 7 per cent is designated for such communities. The remaining 82 per cent of land is owned by governments, private individuals or firms (Rights and Resources Initiative 2023). An estimated 73 per cent of the world's forests are publicly owned versus 22 per cent under private ownership (FAO 2020).

Hence, land tenure, and the different legal rights and arrangements associated with it, directly restricts and influences land-use decision making on the ground.

6.1.2. DEVELOPING SPATIALLY EXPLICIT POLICIES - DATA GAPS AND LESSONS LEARNED

The effectiveness of many of the prioritized instruments in the Innovation Action Pool is often linked to land tenure (Table 7).

TABLE 7**LINKS BETWEEN INNOVATION ACTION POOL POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND LAND TENURE**

INNOVATION ACTION POOL INSTRUMENT	MOST RELEVANT TENURE CATEGORY	LINK TO LAND TENURE
<p>Financial instruments and access to finance (eg payments for environmental services)</p> <p>Taxation and fiscal instruments</p>	<p>Private land tenure, and occasionally indigenous, traditionally, or communally held lands</p>	<p>Financial instruments (such as PES) often require programme participants to have legal and formalized land ownership. This is because a landholder needs to have exclusion rights in order to receive payments or be taxed. This means that they need to be able to prevent third parties from using the given resource (eg deforesting or changing land cover).</p> <p>Financial, taxation and fiscal instruments that are implemented without clearly defined tenure rights may lead to failed implementation, a land rush or overall hardship for biodiversity-dependent people (eg the REDD+ case, see Larson et al. (2013)).</p>
<p>Community participation and local involvement (e.g. community forest management)</p>	<p>Indigenous, traditionally or communally held lands</p>	<p>Evidence often suggests that community managed forests or protected areas are as effective or more effective than strictly protected areas at preventing deforestation (Porter-Bolland et al. 2012; West et al. 2024) or safeguarding biodiversity (Sze et al. 2024). Many argue that this kind of sustainable management is partially due to communities' investment in the long-term sustainability of the resources that livelihoods depend on (Mendelsohn and Balick 1995; Baland and Platteau 1999; Gibson et al. 2000).</p>
<p>State level regulation and hard law</p>	<p>All tenure categories</p>	<p>Regulatory instruments include a broad set of tools that regulate land-use, for instance: the creation of protected areas, the recognition of land claims for indigenous or other local communities, the titling of private lands and specific land-use restrictions.</p> <p>While such land-use regulating instruments may indeed have mixed effectiveness (Santangeli et al. 2023; Li et al. 2024), they remain some of the most effective tools for conserving nature (Soares-Filho et al. 2014; Geldmann et al. 2019). Similarly, when these regulations and laws do not consider specific tenure settings, they may fail to prevent land use change.</p> <p>For instance, in Brazil, lands with poorly defined tenure rights tend to have higher levels of deforestation – likely because lands without a specific owner are difficult to regulate and are at greater risk of land-grabbing (Pacheco and Meyer 2022).</p>

One area of land tenure innovation is integrating improved biodiversity mapping and spatially explicit land tenure mapping. This would mean going beyond standard approaches that treat these issues separately by combining maps with biodiversity indicators with maps of who owns or manages the land. This information can then be used to design and implement tenure-sensitive biodiversity policies and governance mechanisms. However, as mentioned in Table 7, there are many lessons learned from implementations of instruments to reduce biodiversity loss that haven't included tenure-sensitive considerations in the past. These include:

- **The inclusion of Indigenous Peoples and local communities when defining priority areas for biodiversity conservation and restoration in scientific research and recommendations.**

Identifying priority areas for biodiversity conservation and restoration can draw on a range of criteria, including local and regional pressures, ecological uniqueness, connectivity, and the presence of flagship or threatened species. While global biodiversity mapping provides useful context, effective prioritization must be grounded in local realities and needs. It is well known that the highest biodiversity (both in terms of species richness and the presence of rare species) is typically found in the tropics (Jung et al. 2021), and other CLEVER efforts have made additional contributions to such mapping efforts (Oliveira 2024a; Oliveira 2024b; Oliveira and Pacheco 2024). However, mapping and quantifying biodiverse areas can be controversial, particularly when it results in the prioritization of restoration sites in places where there is also high dependency on natural resources for food and livelihoods by local communities because it identifies priority areas for restoration in places where economically poor and marginalized communities depend on natural resources for their livelihoods (Strassburg et al. 2022).

Many communities, including indigenous peoples, smallholders, rural rightsholders

and women often lack secure and formally recognized land tenure. This insecurity stems from historical injustices and ongoing discriminatory governance. Legal property rights can conflict with customary or collective land claims, which undermine human rights and sustainable management. Conservation and restoration efforts must therefore include all rights holders and land users, not just those with legal recognition (UN 2025). In this context, to be locally accepted, implemented and embraced, mapping of areas for biodiversity restoration and conservation can include the people who own or control the land in these areas and should consider their property rights.

- **Spatially explicit land tenure data is needed, but it needs to be fit-for-purpose and sensitive to the needs of specific groups.**

Fit-for-purpose data means collecting enough detail to support good decisions while considering privacy, safety and the unique needs of vulnerable or marginalized groups. In some cases, making such data public can create risks, especially where land rights are contested. Having spatially explicit land tenure data is important because it allows for a myriad of environmental data to be linked more directly to different specific land users. However, spatially explicit land tenure data are lacking for most of the world, both because many land claims remain unrecognized in official systems and because spatial data for many state-recognized titles are often incomplete or inaccessible and are often not publicly available. Though several initiatives have attempted to map global land and forest ownership (Rights and Resources Initiative 2015), these efforts often focus on mapping protected areas or documenting the customary and collective claims of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, rather than public or private lands where formal ownership or state-recognized rights are registered. Public and private lands are frequently the tenure categories under the greatest pressure for conversion to other uses.

A rare and successful case of fit-for-purpose land tenure data collection and collation is Brazil's Rural Environmental Cadastre (CAR for its Portuguese acronym). Rural landowners are compelled to register their property with the CAR, which is primarily an environmental compliance registry and is intended to provide accurate georeferencing of properties for monitoring purposes. While registration is limited to those with formal ownership or recognized rights, inclusion in the CAR does not grant or confirm legal title. In practice, the accuracy of property boundaries depends on the quality of information submitted. Despite such flaws, the CAR allows environmental rules and regulations (eg issuing of fines or embargoes) to be enforced (Gibbs et al. 2015). The CAR also enables detailed studies of land-use changes in these properties (Probst et al. 2020; Pacheco and Meyer 2022). Other countries could take note of this effort for monitoring, enforcement and study of environmental measures in contexts where biodiversity is under threat, but its limitations, including the exclusion of unrecognized rightsholders, underscore the need for sensitivity and inclusivity in similar land tenure data initiatives.

On the other hand, there are cases where making detailed, spatially explicit property data publicly available is not encouraged. Mapping must be sensitive to the needs and security of certain Indigenous Peoples and local communities who do not wish to be findable, as public disclosure may put their land claims, rights or even lives at risk (Garnett et al. 2018).

- **Mapping land tenure enables more effective and targeted biodiversity policies**

An incorrect claim that 80 per cent of the world's biodiversity is found in indigenous lands has been widely circulated. This claim has been repeated across reports and

scientific publications over the past decade yet it has recently been debunked – in fact, around 37 per cent of remaining natural lands, not biodiversity per se, lie within indigenous territories (Fernández-Llamazares et al. 2024).

Clarifying these figures is important because they can shape discourses around who is responsible for enacting biodiversity conservation and restoration. It is crucial not to minimize the role of private landholders³ and, in particular, large landowners. A recent estimate found that more than 70 per cent of global farmland is operated by the one per cent of farms that are over 50 hectares in area (Lowder et al. 2021).

An ongoing project in Brazil has identified private properties and land claims with levels of natural vegetation above (in surplus) and below (in deficit) the levels required by law (Brazil's Forest Code⁴). Properties with surplus are those where deforestation could still legally occur, and properties with deficit are those that are required to restore vegetation in order to duly comply with the law. The study shows that most of both the surplus and deficit native vegetation (by land area) is concentrated on large private properties, simply because they make up the majority of registered rural land in Brazil (Soares-Filho et al. 2024). With these properties covering over 60 per cent of Brazil's territory, it is clear that large private landowners and landholders play a decisive role in biodiversity conservation and restoration (work in progress, see Soares-Filho et al. 2024). Policies and other governance mechanisms targeting these actors would be the most effective. As Table 7 describes, the mechanisms can include financial and fiscal instruments that provide the appropriate incentives for either conservation or restoration of biodiversity in Brazil. For other countries, specific recommendations depend on local land tenure systems and availability of biodiversity data.

³ The term "landholder" refers to people who control or use the land but may not necessarily own it legally.

⁴ Law 12651 of May 25 2012 ([Lei nº 12.651 de 25 de maio de 2012](#)).

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Stakeholder Engagement Workshop in Libreville (Gabon), October 2024.
Credit: Juan Manuel Vargas.

6.2. IMPACT OF STANDARD-LIKE NON-TARIFF MEASURES ON BIODIVERSITY

Non-tariff measures (NTMs) such as sanitary and phytosanitary measures and technical barriers to trade are designed to protect human, animal, and plant health. When aligned with biodiversity protection goals, these measures can safeguard domestic biodiversity from harmful imports and contribute to conservation by restricting trade in wild animals and the spread of invasive species and pathogens. NTMs influence markets through three primary channels. Supply shift impacts occur when increasing compliance requirements lead to higher production costs and reduced supply. Demand shift impacts happen when NTMs incorporating sustainability objectives positively influence consumer demand, helping correct market inefficiencies from production externalities. Administrative cost effects refer to implementation costs that result in higher consumer prices. Policy solutions to optimize NTM effectiveness include developing informative and low-cost NTMs, increasing consumer awareness, harmonizing standards to reduce compliance costs, promoting global coordination, and designing policies that account for negative spillover effects.

6.2.1. USE OF NON-TARIFF MEASURES TO MEET SAFETY AND QUALITY STANDARDS

Non-tariff measures (NTMs) such as sanitary and phytosanitary measures (SPS) (World Trade Organization 1994a) and technical barriers to trade (TBT) (World Trade Organization 1994b) are designed to protect human, animal and plant health. SPSs protect against diseases, pests or contaminants in food and agricultural products (World Trade Organization 1994a), while TBTs set standards for product characteristics, production processes or testing methods to ensure safety, quality or environmental protection (World Trade Organization 1994b).

While the specific requirements of these measures vary widely across countries, their overarching goal is to ensure that regulated products meet safety and quality standards (Tran et al. 2025).

Some NTMs are directly or indirectly related to biodiversity conservation (Ababouch et al. 2023) and are implemented by governments to align market entry requirements with domestic regulatory standards (Tran et al. 2025). When aligned with biodiversity protection goals, these measures can safeguard domestic biodiversity from harmful imports and also contribute to the conservation of biodiversity both domestically and abroad. For example, by influencing production processes and the products that are traded, these measures can restrict activities such as trade in wild animals, spread of invasive species and introduction of pathogens. They may also restrict transport emissions of CO₂ and other pollutants, as well as infrastructure development projects (eg roads and ports) that threaten habitats (Bellora et al. 2020). However, the effectiveness of SPS and TBT measures in curbing harmful trade impacts depends on several factors: how successfully they bring producers into compliance (given the associated costs), consumers' willingness to pay for biodiversity-conserving products and the administrative costs of implementing and enforcing the measures (Tran et al. 2025).

The success of standard-like measures depends on the various impacts they have on producers' profitability and consumers' utility. NTMs influence markets, and consequently producers and consumers, through three primary channels: supply-side impacts, demand-side impacts and administrative cost-related impacts (Jafari and Britz 2018). Effects can vary significantly across countries, depending on factors such as income levels, industry scale and institutional capacity (Anders and Caswell 2009; Santeramo and Lamonaca 2022). The overall outcome depends on how supply and demand conditions, along with administrative costs, interact in response to these regulatory changes (Tran et al. 2025).

6.2.2. IMPACT AND SOLUTIONS TO IMPROVE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES

Supply shift impacts

NTMs often increase production costs by raising either marginal or fixed costs (van Tongeren et al. 2009; Jafari and Britz 2018; Mialhe et al. 2018), which can reduce the quantity of goods that producers are willing to supply at any given price. Several studies highlight that producers in many countries struggle to meet compliance requirements (Anders and Caswell 2009; Shepotylo 2016). However, research also suggests that harmonizing standards can reduce compliance costs and therefore boost production in affected industries (Xiong and Beghin 2014; Shepotylo 2016).

The supply-shifting impact of NTMs is closely linked to disparities in levels of income and industrialization across countries (Anders and Caswell 2009; Xiong and Beghin 2014; Santeramo and Lamonaca 2022). Studies point to significant differences in regulatory enforcement and compliance capacity. For example, studies in high-income countries indicate that compliance costs are often exacerbated by bureaucratic inefficiencies and disconnects between regulations and practical realities (Naylor et al. 2023). In Germany, heavy bureaucratic burdens were found to raise compliance costs (Lasner and Gimpel 2024). In the United States, strong regulation was considered to be a barrier to both compliance and industry growth (Jolly et al. 2023). However, Norway demonstrates that rigorous regulation and robust industry growth can coexist (Naylor et al. 2023). These examples suggest that whilst there is a perception of “excessive regulation” being an obstacle, rigorous standards can be applied successfully when they are cost-effective.

Generally, high-income countries benefit from advanced technologies, which help mitigate the impacts of additional regulations (Tran et al. 2025). In low- and middle-income countries, challenges with regulatory implementation and compliance are frequently linked to internal power struggles, elite capture and contested

political interests, added to institutional capacity constraints (World Bank 2003; Fukuyama 2013; Brinks et al. 2019). These are compounded by issues such as technological gaps and limited financial resources that reflect broader structural inequalities (Tran et al. 2025). For instance, in Brazil, laboratories that test for water quality and pathogens are often inaccessible due to distance or high cost (Valenti et al. 2021). Similarly, in Bangladesh, industry upgrading is hampered by a lack of suitable infrastructure for quality control or for temperature-controlled transport of goods (Ponte et al. 2014). Despite these barriers, export-oriented industries in Thailand, China and Bangladesh have successfully aligned domestic standards with international market requirements, thereby improving adaptability and competitiveness (Ponte et al. 2014; Naylor et al. 2023).

Demand shift impacts

NTMs that incorporate social and environmental objectives can positively influence consumer demand (Xiong and Beghin 2014; Santeramo and Lamonaca 2022). Such objectives can help to correct market inefficiencies that arise from the externalities (unintended social and environmental costs) of production, distribution and consumption (Ababouch et al. 2023). Positive shifts in consumer demand are particularly relevant to biodiversity conservation. For example, fish and seafood are dietary staples in many low- and middle-income countries (Belton et al. 2020) but are sometimes avoided by consumers in other regions due to concerns regarding sustainability, labour practices and food safety of imported fish and seafood (Love et al. 2021; Ababouch et al. 2023). Using biodiversity-conserving standards can help build consumer trust and increase demand for sustainable versions of such products.

The extent of this demand shift depends on how effectively information about NTMs is communicated and how much consumers value the associated attributes. While higher-income international consumers often drive demand for sustainable and traceable products, domestic and lower-income consumers are becoming increasingly influential (Jespersen et al. 2014;

Belton et al. 2020). Furthermore, food safety standards applied to premium or exported products can gradually influence the broader value chain, including lower-end and domestic segments (Jespersen et al. 2014). Over time, widespread adoption of standards in producer markets can raise consumer expectations and narrow the perceived gap in quality between imported and local products (Tran et al. 2025).

Administrative cost effects

The administrative cost effect refers to the costs of implementing standard-like measures, such as increased bilateral import costs related to certification and compliance procedures. While these costs do not directly shift the supply or demand curves, they can result in higher prices for consumers (Jafari and Britz 2018). This in turn may influence consumer behaviour and potentially reduce demand for products that support biodiversity conservation, especially if consumers are price-sensitive.

Optimizing the impact of NTM measures on biodiversity

Given the complex interactions between trade regulations, supply and demand dynamics and biodiversity goals, several policy solutions can enhance the effectiveness of NTMs:

- Develop informative and low-cost NTMs: policymakers should focus on designing measures that are both easy to understand

and inexpensive to comply with. This improves adoption and implementation, not only in resource-constrained settings but also in countries that are already highly regulated.

- Increase consumer awareness: public campaigns, social marketing, and labelling initiatives can help consumers to recognize the value of biodiversity and the safety benefits associated with NTM-compliant products, stimulating demand (Ababouch et al. 2023).
- Support exporters in reducing compliance costs: targeted support, such as subsidies, training and infrastructure investment can help producers in low- and middle-income countries meet international standards without facing prohibitive costs (Ababouch et al. 2023).
- Promote global coordination: international harmonization of standards, mutual recognition of agreements and capacity-building initiatives can help align regulatory efforts and reduce compliance burdens globally (Jolly et al. 2023).
- Design policies that account for the negative spillover effect of policies: policymakers should recognize that producers and traders may not be able to or wish to relocate their production or sourcing regions. Instead, exports might be redirected to alternative destinations with lower or absent NTM requirements, potentially undermining the original policy goals.

CLEVER Final Event in Brussels (Belgium), June 2025.
Credit: Rosa Castañeda.

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6.3. SUPPLY CHAIN DUE DILIGENCE POLICIES

Due diligence obligations ensure businesses take responsibility for operational impacts and act to prevent harm. These process-based requirements compel companies to identify, assess and mitigate risks across activities and relationships using the best available information. Over the past decade, mandatory due diligence has expanded across global supply chains, initially focusing on human rights and increasingly including environmental concerns. Key examples include France’s Duty of Vigilance Law (2017), Germany’s Supply Chains Act (2021), and the EU’s Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (2024). The EU Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR 2023) combines due diligence with bans on non-compliant goods. Best practice design includes addressing the human rights-environment nexus, ensuring accountability across all company sizes and supply chains, and promoting equitable change through fair sourcing. A rightsholder-centred approach engaging workers, Indigenous Peoples, local communities, women and vulnerable groups is essential for effective and equitable outcomes.

6.3.1. EMERGENCE OF MANDATORY DUE DILIGENCE IN ENVIRONMENTAL AND HUMAN RIGHTS LEGISLATION

The purpose of due diligence obligations is to ensure that business enterprises take responsibility for the impacts of their operations

and activities and take corresponding action to prevent harm from occurring. A defining feature of due diligence obligations is that they establish requirements that are process-based rather than outcome-based. Due diligence processes are active and risk-based, requiring businesses to identify, assess and mitigate risks throughout their activities and relationships (Directorate-General for International Partnerships 2022). The accepted benefit of this approach is that it shifts the focus away from enforcing non-compliance and remedying harm, towards preventing harm from occurring in the first place (McCorquodale and Nolan 2021). Due diligence does not require that businesses act on or remove every source of risk in their operations but instead allows businesses to recognize and prioritize risks that are most relevant in their operations using the best available information (Hodge 2025). These risks could include where a corporation’s supply chain, production or sourcing arrangements are associated with risks of deforestation, habitat degradation or species extinction (UNEP FI 2024).

The past decade has seen a noticeable shift in expectations and practices of responsible business conduct and corporate accountability (Del Valle et al. 2021). Reflecting developments at the international level, especially the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (United Nations 2011), some governments and regional economic organizations introduced mandatory due diligence requirements for business conduct that extend throughout a business’s operations, including through their global supply chains. In this way, mandatory due diligence is also a means to address the governance gap in which

multinational corporations were not being effectively held to account for their adverse social or environmental impacts by either the home state, where the corporation was headquartered, or the host state, where the impacts occurred (Outhwaite and Martin-Ortega 2016).

Mandatory due diligence has emerged in several countries. While the focus was initially on human rights, environmental concerns are increasingly included. Examples include France's Duty of Vigilance Law (2017),⁵ Germany's Corporate Due Diligence Obligations in Supply Chains Act (2021),⁶ Italy's Legislative Decree 231/2001,⁷ and the EU's Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (EU CSDDD) (2024).⁸ The EU Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR 2023) takes the regulatory model further by combining mandatory due diligence obligations with a prohibition on regulated products that are not deforestation-free, legally produced in the country of production and covered by a due diligence statement. While mandatory human rights and environmental due diligence (mHREDD) is currently a predominantly European development, proposals are developing across a wider range of countries; currently, Mexico, Brazil and Canada have all proposed legislation⁹ and work continues towards a UN binding treaty on Business and Human Rights¹⁰.

6.3.2. DESIGN AND BEST PRACTICE FOR USING MANDATORY DUE DILIGENCE TO PROMOTE FAIRER AND MORE SUSTAINABLE TRADE

Mandatory due diligence offers possibilities for reforming business accountability and business practices in ways that promote fairer and more sustainable production and consumption. While

mandatory human rights and environmental due diligence legislation (mHREDD) is still relatively new as a regulatory tool, there are already insights into how it can be effectively designed and leveraged to promote sustainable and responsible supply chains.

Mandatory due diligence to act on the human rights-environment nexus

The UN Guiding Principles (UNGP) on Business and Human Rights were crucial in giving legal clarity and momentum to the potential for States to adopt mandatory corporate due diligence measures. Two important developments since the adoption of the UNGPs give further momentum for the close connection of environmental protection with human rights in due diligence. The first was the recognition of the human right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment by the UN General Assembly in 2022 (United Nations General Assembly 2022). The language of the resolution explicitly makes a connection with the UNGPs and the corporate responsibility to respect human rights. The second was the adoption of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF). Target 15 of the KMGBF sets a commitment for Contracting Parties to take measures to encourage, enable and, for large and transnational companies and financial institutions, ensure that "businesses ... assess, disclose and reduce biodiversity-related risks and negative impacts" (Convention on Biological Diversity 2023). This framing reflects the language of human rights diligence and mandatory due diligence that has been identified as a relevant tool for governments to meet Target 15 (Business for Nature and Capitals Coalition 2023). In combination, these developments give additional impetus and legal means for integrating biodiversity and environmental protection into mandatory due diligence (United Nations Special Rapporteur on Human Rights and the Environment 2022).

⁵ Loi relative au devoir de vigilance des sociétés mères et des entreprises donneuses d'ordre

⁶ Act on Corporate Due Diligence Obligations in Supply Chains (Lieferkettensorgfaltspflichtengesetz)

⁷ Legislative Decree 8 June 2001, no. 231, "Regulation on administrative responsibility of legal entities, companies and associations, including those not having legal personality, according to art. 11, Law 29 September 2000, no. 300"

⁸ Directive (EU) 2024/1760 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on corporate sustainability due diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Regulation (EU) 2023/2859

⁹ For legislative summaries and updates on status see <https://www.bhr-law.org/>

¹⁰ See <https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/big-issues/governing-business-human-rights/un-binding-treaty/>

Mandatory due diligence to ensure full business accountability

Mandatory due diligence obligations can vary in scope in a number of important ways, including the minimum size of company subject to regulation, the range of its business relationships that are covered by the regulation, and the reach of the regulation across the supply chain (in other words, how far downstream it applies). While special support may be needed for smaller businesses, good practice suggests that all businesses have responsibilities to protect human rights throughout their business operations, and due diligence therefore should not be restricted to large companies (De Schutter 2020). Likewise, a restrictive approach to the reach of due diligence obligations can, at least from a human rights perspective, be seen as inconsistent with the UNGPs on Business and Human Rights (De Schutter 2020; United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative 2022).

Mandatory due diligence to achieve equitable change

The root cause of human rights violations or environmental harm in global supply chains and other business operations often relates to the sourcing practices of the lead company, such as delivering products to short lead times, and short-term or precarious contractual arrangements (Directorate-General for International Partnerships 2022). mHREDD should lead to changes in sourcing practices. This implies that the lead company (that is subject to the regulation) support producers to meet supply chain needs, including through, for instance, fair wages, secure contracts, technology transfer and capacity-building. The EU CSDDD requires companies to “enter into ‘fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory’ contracts with their business partners, provide ‘targeted and proportionate support’ and bear the cost of independent third-party verifications,

and it clarifies the importance of addressing the impact of the company's purchasing practices” (Dehbi and Martin Ortega 2023; Pietropaoli et al. 2024) .

A key criticism of the EUDR, meanwhile, has been that smallholder producers may incur financial costs, such as those associated with the EUDR's traceability requirements, and could in turn be excluded from EU markets (Gilbert 2024) . The response of regulated companies to the direction under the EUDR that a company's mitigation measures may include “supporting compliance with this Regulation by that operator's suppliers, in particular smallholders, through capacity-building and investments” may therefore be crucial¹¹.

A rightsholder-centred approach to mHREDD is essential for effective and equitable outcomes. Here, “rightsholders” refers to those whose rights may be directly or indirectly affected by company operations, value chains or business relationships, such as workers, Indigenous Peoples, local communities, women and other vulnerable or marginalized groups. This approach implies that mHREDD laws (a) are gender-responsive and inclusive of the most vulnerable rightsholders; and (b) position rightsholder identification, consultation and engagement as fundamental to each stage of the HREDD process. A rightsholder-centred approach to mHREDD design and practice can help to ensure that measures do in fact lead to the desired changes in practices (United Nations Special Rapporteur on Human Rights and the Environment 2022). Similarly, suggestions for increased cooperation between producer and consumer countries, greater inclusion of stakeholders and a do good (rather than do no harm) approach aim to take this further and reduce underlying global power asymmetries (Dehbi and Martin Ortega 2023; Bastos Lima and Schilling Vacaflor 2024).

¹¹ Article 11, EUDR

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6.4. HARNESSING GOVERNMENT PROCUREMENT TO INCENTIVIZE POSITIVE BIODIVERSITY ACTIONS

Public procurement is how governments and public entities purchase goods and services. As both market actors and regulators, governments can use procurement to advance social and environmental goals. Green public procurement (GPP) incorporates requirements designed to promote environmentally responsible purchasing. While GPP has expanded focusing on climate change and decarbonization, biodiversity has attracted limited focus, creating space for innovation. Potential strategies include responsible sourcing in food supply chains, zero-deforestation requirements for timber, and ethical mineral sourcing. Global commitments like the Kunming-Montreal Biodiversity Framework Target 15 and UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights provide a rationale for biodiversity-focused procurement. Innovation can be adaptive and gradually shape goods to meet new standards, or radical, creating entirely new products or systems. However, public procurement alone is not a strong enough tool to address issues such as over-consumption and the underlying drivers of biodiversity loss.

6.4.1. GOVERNMENT USE OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT TO PROMOTE ENVIRONMENTAL OBJECTIVES

Public procurement is the process used by governments and public entities to purchase goods, services and other works. Frequently, this is done by awarding contracts to private suppliers via a competitive public process (Arrowsmith and Kunzlik 2009).

Historically, governments have used the public procurement process, whereby they act as both market actor and regulator, as a tool to simultaneously promote social or environmental objectives – so-called “secondary”, or “horizontal” policies (McCrudden 2007). In this capacity, governments can use public procurement to influence the behaviour of multinational corporations with geographically and contractually dispersed supply chains and operations, by requiring compliance or incentivizing behaviours in line with particular standards (Outhwaite and Martin-Ortega 2016). The requirements of governments, imposed through their public procurement processes and standards, can include far-reaching conditions that cascade through supply chains and business operations (Martin-Ortega et al. 2015). Notably, due diligence requirements have been incorporated into public procurement processes to achieve “responsible” purchasing that extends through global supply chains (OECD 2024a).

To realize the potential of public procurement as a demand-side policy tool to promote positive outcomes for biodiversity requires governments to take advantage of their position as “mega-consumers”. This position in the market affords governments considerable leverage with which to influence their suppliers. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) reports that public procurement expenditure as a share of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) increased significantly across its member countries over the last decade, from 11.8% in 2007 to 12.9% in 2021. On this basis, public procurement has the potential to steer business practices and drive positive environmental outcomes (OECD 2025a).

“Green public procurement” (GPP) refers to the incorporation of requirements designed to promote environmentally responsible or sustainable purchasing into procurement processes. This emerging policy process has the potential to meaningfully contribute towards a government’s environmental commitments (Yukins and Nicholas 2023). Strategies for GPP include (Yukins and Nicholas 2023):

- incorporating environmental considerations into acquisition planning
- considering vendors’ efforts to assess and report the environmental impacts of their products and services as part of vendor qualification
- assessing environmental impacts as part of life cycle costs in evaluating for contract award
- requiring that products or services include a certification or other confirmation (an eco label, for example) reflecting environmental attributes
- weighing environmental impacts, such as greenhouse gas emissions, in technical evaluations for award
- excluding contractors that have failed to honour environmental requirements

6.4.2. APPLYING BIODIVERSITY-CENTRED PUBLIC PROCUREMENT AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR INNOVATION

While interest in GPP has expanded in the past decade, attention has largely focused on climate change commitments and decarbonization. The use of GPP explicitly and strategically in relation to biodiversity has attracted limited focus (OECD 2024b). However, this gap creates space for innovation.

Centring biodiversity within green procurement

Biodiversity may be addressed only marginally by GPP strategies, or mentioned without detailed supporting criteria for monitoring progress, compliance or impact (Hasanbeigi et al. 2019; Stockholm Environment Institute et al. 2023). However, some strategies and initiatives have been adopted in connection with specific drivers of biodiversity loss. These include:

- responsible sourcing requirements in commodity supply chains, for example, in connection with food purchasing (FAO et al. 2021),
- specific zero-deforestation or deforestation-free requirements, relating to commodity supply chains or timber products (McFarland 2018; Falvo and Muscaritoli 2024)
- responsible mineral supply chains (EPRM 2022)

Mapping and aligning the interaction of procurement practices with the drivers of biodiversity loss could provide a systematic means of more fully integrating biodiversity into procurement strategies.

Acting on global commitments and flexibilities

A plethora of global commitments provide both a rationale and an incentive for governments to act on the opportunity for biodiversity-centred public procurement. Green procurement has a recognized role in the Sustainable Development Goals (see UNEP 2021). The Kunming-

Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework commits Parties, through Target 15, to adopt the necessary legal, administrative or policy measures to encourage businesses to regularly monitor, assess and transparently disclose their risks, dependencies and impacts on biodiversity and, in line with Target 14's call, integrate biodiversity into decision-making. In parallel, procurement is not covered by the international trade rules established under the World Trade Organization's (WTO) 1994 General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade. Instead, within the WTO, public procurement has been addressed through the voluntary, plurilateral Government Procurement Agreement (GPA). Developments in the GPA text have clarified that procurement processes can be used to promote environmental aims (WTO 2012). The express provisions and omissions of the GPA also contain a recognized flexibility that can be used to support environmental aims in government procurement, in alignment with trade rules (Anderson et al. 2023). Similarly, global standards, including the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights and the UN Global Compact, actively support the use of public procurement as a means to promote responsible sourcing (Outhwaite and Martin-Ortega 2016).

Identifying the scope for adaptive and radical innovation at the national level

Centring biodiversity in procurement practices and acting on the mandate and opportunities of global commitments and standards provides a clear basis for strategic and impactful integration of biodiversity into public procurement. Tuzi and Filippetti (2024) note that public procurement can bring about policy innovation when used to create a demand for products or services that "do not yet exist and that fulfil certain functions that satisfy human needs or solve societal problems." Procurement innovation can be adaptive, incrementally driving the creation of goods that meet new requirements, or radical, creating completely new products or systems (Tuzi and Filippetti 2024).

Adaptive procurement approaches find ways of making more consistent and/or strategic use of the phases of the procurement process (eg technical specifications or award criteria) to promote more sustainable purchasing. For example, by building on "whole life cycle" purchasing provisions (Pouikli 2021), or by reflecting regulatory shifts such as the inclusion of corporate due diligence requirements into public procurement criteria (OECD 2024a). Adaptive legal frameworks can ensure that national procurement legislation enables full inclusion of biodiversity objectives (Yukins and Nicholas 2023).

More radical procurement innovation may take a wider and more expansive economic focus in public procurement. Radical approaches can include more extensive use of mandatory requirements, including mandatory green procurement, which has already been adopted in a limited number of countries and contexts (OECD 2024b). Similarly, outcome-focused approaches to public procurement are reflected in other innovative green procurement strategies, such as setting targets for the proportion of contracts incorporating GPP, as well as the use of monitoring and reporting mechanisms (OECD 2024b). Appropriate methodologies, support and capacity-building are essential to enabling the successful uptake of such strategies (OECD 2024b).

Lastly, public procurement aligns to some degree with a neoliberal economic model and is poorly equipped to address over-consumption and related underlying drivers of biodiversity loss. Decision-making on procurement practices should therefore take into account long-term consumption levels and patterns, and integrate principles such as inter-generational equity as well as other dimensions of equity (Uehara 2020).

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CLEVER Annual Meeting in Bonn (Germany), November 2024.
Credit: Rosa Castañeda.

6.5. PARTICIPATORY APPROACH TO FOREST GOVERNANCE

Public participation is a central element of environmental decision-making and is essential for good governance and sustainability transitions. Public participation allows citizens with diverse perspectives to engage in environmental and natural resource decisions. Stakeholders may include ministries, civil society, Indigenous Peoples, local communities, the private sector, NGOs, and experts. Meaningful participation builds trust between state and non-state actors and enhances legitimacy of government decisions. In the context of timber industry, involving relevant stakeholders in developing or reforming laws on legal and sustainable harvest, processing, and trade is key to inclusive legal frameworks and effective compliance. The FLEGT Voluntary Partnership Agreements process offers best practice lessons: ensuring broad representation through stakeholder mapping; enabling meaningful dialogue by providing timely access to information; and maintaining engagement through public reporting on progress, sustained technical support, and effective leadership. Representative deliberative processes involving deeper deliberation by well-informed groups are recognized to deliver better policy outcomes.

6.5.1. THE BENEFITS OF PUBLIC PARTICIPATION IN ENVIRONMENTAL LAWMAKING

Effective national laws are key to protecting and managing the world's forests, particularly when designed collaboratively with full and effective participation of stakeholders (Faure et al. 2020; Kwon and Ward 2021). Public participation has become a central facet of environmental decision-making and is regarded as essential for good governance and transitioning into sustainability (Akerboom and Craig 2022; European Environment Agency. 2023; O'Brien et al. 2025). Including relevant stakeholders in

the creation or reform of laws concerning the legal and sustainable harvest, processing, and trade in timber is key to developing effective and inclusive legal frameworks, guarding against inadvertent discrimination against certain stakeholder groups, and facilitating compliance and enforcement (Kwon and Ward 2021).

Public participation refers to the ability of citizens representing different perspectives to be involved in environmental or natural resource decision-making (Akerboom and Craig 2022). It is a voluntary process where people can exchange information, ideas and opinions, with the potential to influence the result (Bruña-García and Marey-Pérez 2014). In the development of legal texts, stakeholders may include ministries and other relevant government agencies, civil society, local communities and indigenous populations, the private sector, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and experts (Faure et al. 2020). Involving communities most likely to be impacted, including marginalized groups, may contribute specialized knowledge and local understanding of complexities. That can improve the content of laws by ensuring the consideration of local needs and rights of the communities affected.

Engagement with a broad and diverse range of stakeholders is important, particularly those most directly impacted by decisions. The New York Declaration on Forests (NYDF) recognizes that inclusion of Indigenous Peoples, local communities and traditional knowledge in solutions to protect forests is essential (NYDF 2014). Recent priority actions call for strengthening of legal frameworks, implemented through inclusive and participatory approaches (Forest Declaration Assessment 2025). Likewise, the IPBES Transformative Change assessment stresses the importance of recognizing and incorporating the views and values of Indigenous Peoples and local communities in delivering transformative change, including the involvement of diverse stakeholders in decision-making (O'Brien et al. 2025).

Including all relevant stakeholder groups in the drafting or reform of national forest laws will help ensure that laws benefit from a broader knowledge base and diverse viewpoints and should also ensure that the rights of affected people and groups are respected. Meaningful participation of all relevant stakeholder groups can build trust between state and non-state actors and increase the acceptance and legitimacy of government decisions, leading to greater compliance and effective implementation (Faure et al. 2020; Akerboom and Craig 2022). Laws that are well implemented and enforced will ultimately lead to greater protection, conservation and management of forests.

There are varying levels of participation, ranging from informing stakeholders about a process (generally passive and unidirectional) to consulting, involving, collaborating and empowering to influence outcomes. Public participation can have an increasing impact along the scale from informing to empowering, although the most effective level of engagement is context-specific. Whatever the level of engagement, the general approach is credited with fostering more inclusive, transparent, accountable and adaptive governance systems (Hoare et al. 2020; Fernandes et al. 2024; O'Brien et al. 2025).

6.5.2. Best practice and lessons learned through the FLEGT VPA process

Public participation in environmental decision-making is not a new idea; indeed, it is a legal right for Parties to the Aarhus Convention (Europe and Central Asia) and the Escazu Agreement (Latin America and the Caribbean), and is recognized expressly in relation to the rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNECE 1998; UNDRIP 2007; UN 2021). It is also part of environmental policymaking in the United States and Canada (Parkins and Sinclair 2023). However, it is not standard practice in many forest and biodiversity-rich countries where recent stakeholder participation in the drafting of forest laws and policies yields an increasing knowledge base around best practice (Satyal 2018; Kwon and Ward 2021; Baldessari et al. 2024).

For example, the negotiation and implementation of FLEGT Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs) – bilateral agreements between the EU and timber producer countries – have broad stakeholder participation at their core (EUFLEGT Facility 2014). In some countries, VPA negotiations marked the first time civil society had participated in decision-making, with governments, civil society organizations (CSOs) and Indigenous Peoples working together where there was no previous tradition (Fern 2019; Kwon and Ward 2021; Mvoukani 2021).

Core lessons for effective multi-stakeholder participation learned throughout the VPA process included (Satyal 2018; Fern 2019; Hoare et al. 2020; Kwon and Ward 2021):

Ensuring broad representation

- Identify all relevant sectors and stakeholder groups (including through stakeholder mapping).
- Allow stakeholder groups to select their representatives.
- Consider appropriate levels of participation (eg CSO representatives versus direct representation) and appropriate consultation methods, depending on local context (eg national/regional workshops, direct interviews, online public consultation, multi-stakeholder platforms).
- Consider how power dynamics might affect certain stakeholder groups' ability or willingness to participate. Where necessary, host separate meetings for specific groups to enable their equitable participation.
- Facilitate participation of typically underrepresented groups such as women, Indigenous Peoples and youth, alongside micro, small and medium enterprises by addressing logistical barriers and providing necessary financial support to enable their participation.

Ensuring meaningful dialogue

- Provide sufficient and timely access to information and documents, with adequate time to digest and prepare a response.

- Support the capacity of stakeholders to contribute effectively (which may include dedicated financial and technical support, capacity-building, training etc.).
- Involve civil society stakeholders from an early stage to ensure their views and perspectives are properly taken into account.
- Organize consultations to be facilitated or led by fair, objective, credible partners with adequate knowledge of the process, topic and local contexts.
- Involve political decision makers of legal reform throughout the consultation process, promoting co-ownership by both state and non-state actors.
- Ensure credible channels to incorporate stakeholder inputs into the legal text (eg a Legal Working Group to draft legislative suggestions).
- Provide a mechanism through which stakeholders can see how information is used.
- Provide effective and consistent leadership including: clear and transparent communication; technical competence and background knowledge; a clear decision-making framework; fair and effective facilitation; and strong political will.

In terms of the quality of public decision-making processes, the “representative deliberative process” has grown in popularity between 2010 and 2020 and is recognized to deliver better policy outcomes (OECD 2020). Compared to participatory processes that aim to involve a larger proportion of affected people, deliberative processes involve deeper deliberation of complex topics by a smaller but representative group of people who are well informed about the topic. Drawing on evidence from 282 case studies from OECD Member countries, the OECD considered that institutionalizing deliberative processes could potentially enhance trust in governments, provide greater legitimacy to make hard choices and improve practices by ensuring collective learning and experimentation (OECD 2020).

Maintain engagement and confidence of stakeholders throughout the process

- Report publicly on timelines and progress (eg publish on government websites).
- Provide adequate and sustained technical support and capacity-building to stakeholders throughout the process, including to support eventual compliance.

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6.6. ECOLOGICAL TAXES AND OTHER FISCAL INCENTIVES¹²

Government forest services in many regions have faced budget cuts due to financial crises, weakening monitoring and control systems and creating favourable conditions for illegal logging. This has prompted a shift from command-and-control approaches to incentive-based policies like environmental taxes. Tax systems raise revenue and influence behaviour through (dis)incentives. Environmental taxes include regular taxes earmarked for green projects and ecological (Pigouvian) taxes targeting harmful activities, reducing their profitability while generating funds for conservation or restoration. The “bonus-malus” mechanism is an example of taxing unsustainable practices more heavily and rewarding sustainable ones using surplus funds, maintaining budget neutrality. Gabon applied this in 2020 by introducing forest tax levels based on certification status, which quickly increased certification uptake. Effective tax incentives require comprehensive fiscal policies, including clear land rights, strong monitoring, penalties for illegal activity, access to credit, and quality infrastructure. Transparent benefit-sharing systems are essential to ensure fairness and accountability.

6.6.1. FISCAL MEASURES FOR SUSTAINABLE FORESTRY

Government forest services across many regions have experienced significant budget reductions in recent decades, largely due to financial crises that have necessitated substantial cuts in public spending. This, along with several other factors, has compromised the effectiveness of monitoring and control mechanisms, while creating favourable conditions for illegal logging operations. The proliferation of illegal activities has exerted downward pressure on timber prices, which in

turn has reduced the economic viability and profitability of legal and sustainable forestry practices (Karsenty 2021). This, in turn, led academics and policymakers working on promoting sustainable forest management to shift their focus from command-and-control approaches towards incentive-based policies, such as environmental taxes, that reward sustainable behaviour (Hansen and Lund 2018).

This section focuses on environmental taxes in tropical countries and not, for example, on corporate taxes, which seem to have a limited effect on companies' actions regarding sustainable practices (Hansen and Lund 2018). Tax systems have two main functions. Taxes are used by the state (or other governing body) to collect revenue or to steer behaviour by creating (dis)incentives that (dis)encourage actors to implement certain actions (Karsenty 2010). There are two different mechanisms to apply environmental taxes:

- i. Regular taxes (such as income or sales tax) can be used to create revenue that the government earmarks for environmental projects. This type of tax is used to raise money for green causes, but it may not directly change the behaviour of the actors that are causing environmental damage (Karsenty 2024).
- ii. Ecological taxes, or Pigouvian taxes, apply to activities or their outputs that are known to cause environmental damage (Perman et al. 2003). These taxes work by reducing the profitability of environmentally harmful activities, making them economically less attractive, while simultaneously generating revenues that can be invested in nature conservation, restoration, or research into cleaner technologies and production practices (Karsenty 2021).

In the context of forestry in tropical countries, the state often owns the forests and is entitled to collect “rent” for their use. There are specific

¹² This section on fiscal incentives and ecological taxes was written by CLEVER researchers for the audience of the Innovation Action Pool and is largely based on the work of Dr. Alain Karsenty (CIRAD). The main report used as a source of information is Karsenty 2021.

taxation mechanisms that can be applied to forests. Taxes can be collected based on the allowed cut area, stumpage volume, felled volume (with or without differentiating between less and more valuable tree species), volume of logs entering the mill, volume of processed products or volume of products exported. Forest taxation tends to combine several of these. The benefit of an “upstream” tax (eg based on the logs entering versus leaving the mill) is that it incentivizes waste reduction in the production process. However, the simplest version of upstream taxes, based on felling area, poses a risk to companies as it creates a fixed cost that does not consider price fluctuations, changing weather conditions, security issues, or other uncertainties (Karsenty 2010). Government policies may have unintended consequences even when they successfully address specific issues. For example, policies promoting more efficient timber processing may increase industrial demand, leading to more intensive harvesting that might reduce timber and fuelwood availability for local communities (FAO and EFI 2018).

Economically used land, including land used for agricultural purposes, can also be taxed directly. Research suggests that such taxes have the potential to enhance economic development while simultaneously promoting land conservation as efficiently as environmental regulations or protected areas (Kalkuhl and Edenhofer 2017; Schuster et al. 2018).

Government tax policies can play a significant role in guiding land users (ie forestry companies and farmers) towards more sustainable practices. FAO and EFI (2018) published a comprehensive document on forest concession voluntary guidelines. The guidelines advise governments to apply financial and fiscal instruments, with an emphasis placed on selecting an appropriate instrument. One of the recommended instruments is granting tax relief for concessionaires who improve

their economic, environmental and/or social performance. This is an example of forestry ecotax or preferential fiscal treatment.

Beyond forestry, taxes have also recently been proposed as a means to reduce the environmental and biodiversity impacts of trade in food and non-food biomass products (Heine et al. 2021). Here the main principle is that bio-based commodity trade, while producing economic benefits for both exporting and importing regions, causes environmental damages and biodiversity losses mainly in exporting regions. These regions are often low or middle-income countries with limited environmental governance capacities. Small tax rates on these trade flows could generate substantial and continuous flows of tax revenues to finance targeted nature conservation and restoration actions in regions where such investments have the highest potential impact.

6.6.2. FROM PREFERENTIAL TAX TREATMENT TO MANDATORY CERTIFICATION

The bonus-malus mechanism¹³

The “bonus-malus” mechanism is an example of an ecotax that creates behavioural change. Non-sustainable action is taxed more heavily, and the tax surplus created is used to reward companies that adhere to sustainable practices (Karsenty 2024). Bonus-malus is an appealing option for the state because it is budget-neutral, as the bonus is financed by the malus. The instrument is a textbook example of an ecotax, whose sole purpose is to trigger change towards sustainable action (Karsenty 2024). Bonus-malus is best known from the field of low-emission vehicles. For example, France uses this system to encourage people to buy electric cars. Those buying an electric car get money back from the government (the “bonus”), while those buying a polluting car pay extra tax (the “malus”) (Kara and Leal-Arcas 2023).

¹³ The example of bonus-malus mechanisms is fully based on the ideas of Dr. Alain Karsenty (CIRAD) and the brief written by him in 2024: <https://archive2020-24.pfbc-cbfp.org/news-partner/Alain-Karsenty-Cirad-note.html>

To consider this in the forestry context, from 2020, the Gabonese government¹⁴ introduced three levels of forest tax, depending on whether the forest has a forest management certification (the company receives a tax reduction), a legality certification (the company undergoes a moderate tax increase), or no certification (a high tax increase). After the introduction of the scheme, the number of logging companies entering forest management or legality certification processes rose rapidly. Although the Gabon example is not a bonus-malus mechanism, as the aim is not budget neutrality but increasing tax revenue, the principle remains the same. The sourcing of tax revenue by punishing non-sustainable businesses makes it possible to grant tax relief to reward companies that join forest management certification programs (Karsenty 2024). The source of tax income for the government gradually shifts from malus to bonus, or from non-certified to certified, with the total income remaining stable (or, in the case of Gabon, increasing).

In theory, the effect of a successful bonus-malus system is that, over time, there will be no unsustainable forest units or companies left, because they either comply with the expected sustainability criteria or become uncompetitive due to heavy taxes. The ratio of malus and bonus is balanced so that the level of bonus decreases as more companies join certification schemes, and the level of penalty for non-certification increases. This also discourages operators from returning to uncertified production. When most companies have reached the sustainability goal, the bonuses can be phased out, as certification has become the new normal (Karsenty 2024).

Fiscal instruments have potential if introduced together with other appropriate economic and policy instruments

Karsenty (2010; 2021)¹⁵ proposed other fiscal and non-fiscal tools that can be used to support the implementation of ecotaxes. These include:

- An alternative market-based tax setting system, where concessions are allocated based on competitive bidding (auctions), as has been in use in Cameroon since 1997.
- Differentiating tax rates among tree species to promote the (sustainable) harvesting of lesser-used timber species.
- Combining the previous with tax rates determined according to location and transport costs. This would provide an incentive for reducing the selective harvesting of only high-value trees in remote areas.

Forest taxation can help promote sustainable forest management in tropical regions, but it requires a realistic approach (Hansen and Lund 2018). Tax measures cannot be implemented in isolation; rather, a comprehensive set of policies is needed to target the entire fiscal regulatory framework (Karsenty 2010). Additionally, a stable investment environment for forests depends on factors including clear land rights, effective monitoring and implementation of taxation, penalties for illegal activities, access to credit and quality infrastructure (Karsenty 2021). It is also important to consider how new fiscal instruments may affect economic, ecological and social environments, as well as local communities. To ensure fairness and accountability, transparent benefit distribution systems should be established for collected fees, taxes and royalties, with agreed shares distributed among stakeholders (FAO and EFI 2018).

¹⁴ The Forest Code of the Democratic Republic of Congo also mentions "the establishment of a forest taxation policy to guarantee sustainable management of the forest resource, an incentive for good forest management practices, and conciliation of forest management objectives" as an important measure: <https://www.atibt.org/en/news/12212/republic-of-congo-the-new-forest-code-promulgated>

¹⁵ See Karsenty 2021 for further recommendations and more case studies in Brazil, Cambodia, the Congo, Côte d'Ivoire, Myanmar, Peru, Thailand and Viet Nam.

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6.7. SUSTAINABILITY CERTIFICATIONS: AN EXAMPLE FROM THE AQUACULTURE SECTOR

Sustainability certifications are privately designated seals that distinguish products based on environmental attributes not visible to consumers. These labels help producers access environmentally conscious markets, though price premiums are often low. Instead, certification offers entry into exclusive markets. Evidence on certifications' ability to reduce environmental and social impacts is mixed. Optimal societal outcomes usually require complementary policies, such as bans on harmful products and financial incentives linked to environmental performance. Aquaculture, despite its nutritional and economic benefits, threatens biodiversity through unsustainable feed sourcing, invasive species, eutrophication, and habitat destruction. Certification schemes like Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), Best Aquaculture Practices (BAP), and GLOBALG.A.P. cover 5% of global aquaculture and address biodiversity risks through feed indicators and farm-location criteria that prevent establishment in protected areas. Critics argue these schemes overlook far-field impacts. Innovations such as before-and-after analysis supported by remote sensing and high-resolution land and ocean use data can improve impact monitoring.

6.7.1. EMERGENCE AND SCOPE OF SUSTAINABILITY CERTIFICATIONS

Sustainability or eco-certifications are privately designated seals that differentiate products based on environmental sustainability attributes otherwise invisible to consumers. These labels enable producers to reach environmentally conscious consumers by communicating environmental footprints associated with using or consuming a product (Swartz et al. 2017). In certification schemes, price premiums for producers are often low. Instead of offering higher payments, certification schemes can be appealing to producers due to the entry they provide into exclusive markets (Lambin et al. 2018).

There is conflicting evidence in the literature regarding the potential of certification to reduce environmental and social impacts (Lambin et al. 2018). For example, the complexity and proliferation of different eco-labels hamper their effectiveness in guiding consumers (Yokessa and Marette 2019; Rezazga et al. 2024). Ecolabels and certification schemes provide value yet fall short of being comprehensive solutions for ecological improvement. Achieving optimal societal outcomes typically requires integrating certification with complementary policy instruments, including prohibitions on harmful products and financial incentives or penalties tied to environmental performance (Yokessa and Marette 2019).

This section examines aquaculture certification through fishmeal production, a key focus area within the CLEVER project. This analysis addresses three critical aspects: the complexities of assessing sustainability certification impacts at scale, the importance of creating financial motivations for producers to participate in certification schemes, and the potential of satellite-based monitoring technologies to enhance verification processes.

Despite its well-documented nutritional and economic benefits, aquaculture poses growing threats to biodiversity in both marine and terrestrial ecosystems. Marine-related threats often result from unsustainable feed sourcing, such as using bycatch from fishing methods that damage seafloor biodiversity (Gephart et al. 2021). On land, aquaculture contributes to ecological degradation through the introduction of invasive species, marine and freshwater eutrophication (nutrients leaking from fertilizers used on farms) and the destruction of ecologically important habitats, particularly mangrove ecosystems (Gephart and Golden 2022).

In response to these concerns, a number of organizations, such as World Wildlife Fund, Global Seafood Alliance, and the Euro-Retailer Produce Working Group, have initiated sustainability certification schemes (Bush et al. 2013; Rector et al. 2023). These certifications are often considered as hybrid governance,

combining private sector and community governance and minimal involvement from the state government (Vince and Haward 2019). The underlying idea of certification is straightforward: to leverage the purchasing power of consumers in high-income markets to influence production practices in biomass-exporting countries, where national governance capacity can be weak (Partelow et al. 2025).

The preference for certified aquaculture products is present not only in high-income markets such as the United States and Germany but also in lower-income markets like Viet Nam (Hammarlund et al. 2025). The three most prominent sustainable aquaculture certifications are Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), Best Aquaculture Practices (BAP), and GLOBALG.A.P. (Bush et al. 2013; Rector et al. 2023). These three certification schemes accredit around 5% of global aquaculture production (Bush et al. 2013).

Definition of sustainability and the challenge in measuring large-scale impacts

How do sustainability certifications address biodiversity threats in aquaculture and define the criteria accordingly? For the marine-related biodiversity concerns, the three large certification schemes include feed ingredient indicators. These indicators include the Fish in Fish out (FIFO) ratio, which reflects the amount of marine wild-caught fish used to feed a unit weight of harvested aquaculture product. In addition, farms are required to document the sources of feed supply to ensure traceability and environmental accountability (Aquaculture Stewardship Council 2023; Best Aquaculture Practices 2023; GLOBALG.A.P. 2024).

When it comes to the aquafarm sites, certifications include farm-location criteria to mitigate biodiversity threats. Farms are typically required to not be established inside protected areas, natural wetlands and critical habitats of endangered species. Other criteria include maintaining buffers between farms and marine environments and movement corridors for

native wildlife. As a common critical argument of certification, sceptics suspect that this focus on certifying sites overlooks large-scale far-field impacts (Bush et al. 2013; Rector et al. 2023). Exploring the large-scale perspective of sustainability certifications would not only strengthen their credibility but also assist interested stakeholders in monitoring and supporting biodiversity conservation.

How sustainable aquaculture certifications create large-scale impact

Shrimp farming has widely been considered the leading cause of mangrove loss (Goldberg et al. 2020). In response, sustainability certifications have been promoted to encourage environmentally responsible practices (Watanabe and Ubukata 2023). Economic incentives drive shrimp farmers' decisions to seek certification. Producers are motivated by the expectation of price premiums and improved market access (Dong et al. 2021; Watanabe and Ubukata 2023). While eligibility for certification often depends on historical land use (eg farms established before the 1999 cut-off), farms can compensate by rehabilitating mangrove areas to qualify for certification (Aquaculture Stewardship Council 2023).

The impact of sustainable aquaculture certifications on mangrove outcomes depends on economic motivations and behavioural responses within local areas. These dynamics can create both positive and negative large-scale effects. On the positive side, certified farms can serve as demonstration models, benefiting from higher prices and international market access, which encourages local uptake of certification and collective mangrove conservation efforts. However, strengthening environmental stewardship in one area could displace mangrove-destructive activities to nearby locations (ie negative spillover effects). The perceived success of certified farms might also attract new producers and encourage aquaculture expansion in nearby areas, potentially offsetting mangrove gains achieved through rehabilitation.

6.7.2. INNOVATIONS FOR LARGE-SCALE IMPACT MONITORING: BEFORE-AND-AFTER ANALYSIS SUPPORTED BY REMOTE SENSING

Measuring the large-scale effect of sustainability certifications can be challenging due to the lack of comparison points (ie what would have happened in the absence of certification). A recent study by Rico-Straffon et al. (2023) compared eco-certified and non-certified forest logging concessions in the Amazon, but did not find significant impacts on forest loss. Another study by Tran (2025) aims to do a similar comparison of the mangrove ecosystem. The idea of the study is to match areas with certified farms with a control group of similar but non-certified areas. Matching can be based on geographical factors (eg distance to nearest roads) or historical land-use patterns (eg historical mangrove coverage, or area changes of rice, aquaculture and urban use). In principle, the method quantifies how mangrove ecosystems change due to certification by eliminating other factors that might influence the outcomes.

Certification schemes such as FSC's GIS Portal, which provides auditors with geospatial data and satellite imagery to assess compliance, increasingly integrate remote sensing into their monitoring processes (FSC 2025). The rise of publicly available remote-sensing-based and high-resolution land-use data can also facilitate academic analyses of certification effectiveness. Similarly, the Global Mangrove Watch provides global data on mangrove extent (Bunting et al. 2022) and could be used for monitoring purposes. Other mangrove-related datasets at a smaller scale also exist and include country-specific land-use categories such as rice paddies (eg van Truong et al. 2024). The benefit of these datasets is that they cover a long period, which allows for temporal comparisons. For example, they can show conditions before and after the ASC Shrimp Standard cut-off point in May 1999, after which shrimp farms built on cleared mangroves became ineligible for ASC certification (Aquaculture Stewardship Council 2023b).

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6.8. STRENGTHENING FOREST GOVERNANCE THROUGH INDEPENDENT MONITORING

Independent forest monitoring (IFM) involves third parties verifying forestry activities for compliance with legal and regulatory standards. It encompasses diverse approaches that enhance credibility and strengthen law enforcement through participatory, evidence-based tools. Civil society and forest communities increasingly detect and report infringements. IFM emerged in 1999 through formal contracts between governments and international NGOs, spreading across Congo Basin countries. It has evolved to include mandated and non-mandated forms with greater involvement from national and local civil society. IFM contributes to FLEGT Voluntary Partnership Agreements and REDD+ processes and has expanded to social obligations and sectors like mining and agriculture. Strengthening IFM requires national strategies, legal recognition, and investment in quality control. Networks like RENOI in the Democratic Republic of Congo can improve cost efficiency. Cameroon's SNOIE became the first civil society monitoring system certified to ISO 9001:2015. Technologies like ForestLink, Forest Watcher, and satellite systems support community-led monitoring.

6.8.1. EMERGENCE OF INDEPENDENT FOREST MONITORING AND BROADER COMMUNITY VIGILANCE APPROACHES

Corruption and weak governance lead to high risks of illegal deforestation in many tropical forest countries, with civil society and forest communities playing an increasing role in detection and reporting on infringements (Forest Declaration Assessment 2023). Independent forest monitoring (IFM) is where third parties (actors external to the government) monitor forestry activities to verify compliance (Yamauchi-Mansur-Levy et al. 2022). IFM is a key component of international strategies to improve forest governance and address illegalities in the forest sector (Brack and Léger 2013; FAO 2021; Vallée et al. 2022).

IFM can be defined as “a third-party assessment of the conformity of forest management and forestry activities with the legislative and regulatory standards in force in the forestry sector of the country” (Mbzibain et al. 2023). Rather than a specific tool or system, it represents a diversity of approaches and initiatives that aim to improve credibility and initiatives that aim to improve credibility in the forest sector and promote stronger law enforcement (De Sy et al. 2016). IFM is a participatory approach in which organized civil society and independent professionals can influence the sector's transparency and governance using evidence-based tools, processes and data (Yamauchi-Mansur-Levy et al. 2022).

Civil society has long been involved in the protection and monitoring of forest resources. However, the term IFM first emerged in 1999, with early initiatives centred on a formal service contract between a government entity and an international non-governmental organization (NGO) (Brack and Léger 2013). The approach spread, particularly to countries of the Congo Basin. As the concept evolved, there was an emergence of both mandated and non-mandated IFM, with greater involvement of national and local civil society organizations (CSOs) and environmental associations.

Independent observation has a core role in some FLEGT Voluntary Partnership Agreements (eg for monitoring timber legality assurance systems), and the IFM methodology was also adopted for scrutiny of various REDD+¹⁶ processes (eg pilot project implementation and ensuring respect for REDD+ safeguards) (EUFLEGT Facility 2022; EUREDD 2022). Individual countries may have many monitors, with mandated IFM organizations working alongside non-mandated organizations with varying levels of collaboration (Brack and Léger 2013; Mbzibain et al. 2023). The scope of IFM has also expanded beyond monitoring of activities in forest concessions to include social obligations and sectors such as mining and agriculture (Nyirenda and Mbzibain 2020).

In Latin America, there is growing recognition of the role of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IP and LCs) as forest defenders in, for example, monitoring deforestation, illegal logging and mining activities within their territories. Countries display various “forest vigilance” approaches and mechanisms. Like IFM, these approaches hold considerable potential to improve forest governance and legality verification (Yamauchi-Mansur-Levy et al. 2022).

IFM's pathway to change is that decision makers use the data and evidence generated by independent monitors to inform policies, strengthen law enforcement and address legality risks in the forest sector. This should

lead to improved forest governance, a reduction in illegal logging and ultimately, longer-term environmental, economic and social benefits (Vallée et al. 2022). The quality and credibility of the findings of independent monitors and the receptiveness of government and industry actors are therefore key to IFM's success. Increased transparency and information does not guarantee improved forest governance; it depends on the political economy, institutional environment and other enabling factors.

6.8.2. LESSONS LEARNED AND ADOPTION OF INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES

How to strengthen and scale up

One key lesson emerging from IFM implementation across different national contexts is the value of a national level strategy that creates a clear vision, coordinates activities undertaken by different CSOs and separates roles (eg lobbying conducted by different organizations from independent monitors) (Hoare et al. 2020). Legal recognition of IFM is beneficial in promoting widespread acceptance by government and industry stakeholders, facilitating access to public information and providing protection for whistleblowers (Nyirenda and Mbzibain 2020). For example, in Indonesia, IFM is enshrined in the EU-Indonesia VPA and the rights of independent forest monitors are acknowledged in the forestry regulations, providing protection from threats, access to sites and eligibility for sustainable financing (FAO 2021).

Investment in quality control and quality assurance systems is needed to raise the credibility of IFM (Vallée et al. 2022). Cost efficiencies can also be attained by developing networks or communities of practice. In the Democratic Republic of the Congo, the development of RENOI, a national network of mandated and non-mandated IFM organizations, enables members to follow a shared methodology, coordinate closely and observe separate roles (EUREDD 2022).

¹⁶ REDD stands for “Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation in developing countries”. It is a framework established countries framework to protect forests as part of the Paris Agreement. <https://unfccc.int/topics/land-use/workstreams/redd/what-is-redd>

Cameroon's Standardized External Independent Monitoring System (Système normalisé d'observation indépendante externe; SNOIE) is an innovative example of scaling-up, ensuring quality standards, and providing stronger coordination across organizations (FAO 2021). SNOIE was developed by FODER in collaboration with other CSOs. SNOIE became the first civil society monitoring system to become certified, conforming to the international standard ISO 9001:2015 (CIDT 2018).

SNOIE is a set of standardized monitoring processes, providing a guarantee of quality from the initial observation and verification of potential forest infractions through to reporting and advocacy. The system ensures clearly defined and separate roles, provision of training for observers and a rigorous approach to providing independent, documented evidence in a systematic way (Hoare et al. 2020; CIDT and FODER 2021). SNOIE is widely acknowledged to have helped civil society advocate more effectively, prompting increased government accountability and enforcement in the forest sector (Hoare et al. 2020; FODER 2024). By bringing the work of CSOs up to international quality standards, SNOIE helps to address illegal logging and provides accurate information for regulatory requirements such as the EU Timber Regulation, the United States Lacey Act and, in future, the EU Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (CIDT and FODER 2021).

The application of IFM could be broadened. Employing new investigative and analytical techniques could address wider forms of forest crime, as well as monitoring decisions and actions in other sectors, such as deforestation-free commitments, illegal wildlife trade, or implementation of targets in nationally determined contributions (NDCs) (Hoare et al. 2020; FODER 2024). In Indonesia, the NGO Kaoem Telapak has built a network of independent forest monitors to tackle deforestation and forest crimes and to protect the rights of IP and LCs. Independent monitors are integral to Indonesia's Timber

Legality Assurance System and, since 2020, the Indonesian Sustainable Palm Oil certification. Capacity for IFM has recently expanded by working with indigenous youths in regions threatened by the expansion of large-scale plantations, mining, and infrastructure projects (Kaoem Telapak 2024). In 2025, a forest monitoring platform (Ground Truthed.id) was launched to support compliance with the EUDR by providing real-time, geolocation-based evidence on illegalities relating to timber and palm oil production (Jong 2025; Tumbelaka et al. 2025).

South-south cooperation can help amplify IFM's impacts. Examples of cooperation include exchanging knowledge on monitoring techniques and capacity-building between IFM networks, undertaking cross-border investigations and conducting joint advocacy (Minangsari 2024).

State-of-the-art tools and technologies

As an evolving approach, independent monitoring is embracing emerging technologies and digitalization, combined with community-led approaches, to strengthen its capabilities and promote transparency, public participation and government accountability (Adam and Fazekas 2021). Co-design and co-management of technological solutions with forest communities and considerations around data ownership and local contexts can help ensure that innovations are inclusive and benefit local actors.

For example, the ForestLink satellite alert system provides an easy-to-use technology (mobile application) for community monitors to send real-time alerts about illegal activities in their territories. ForestLink allows observers to gather rigorous georeferenced information and send it via satellite from remote areas (Rainforest Foundation UK 2023). In Peru, it is used by the indigenous organization FENAMAD to help document illegal logging and mining activities and encourage a more efficient state

response. By integrating a new technological tool in an existing mechanism developed by indigenous organizations, the project has achieved successful results and improved coordination with government authorities (Rainforest Foundation UK 2023).

Other remote sensing technologies providing near-real-time information freely downloadable on smartphones include apps like Forest Watcher and FLEGT Watch. Forest Watcher allows easy offline access to data about forest change from Global Forest Watch, enabling forest monitors, indigenous communities and law enforcement to view data on their devices (Petersen and Pintea 2017). FLEGT Watch enables observers to receive deforestation alerts in their specified monitoring areas, to make observations that are automatically geocoded and dated and to generate mission reports (VisioTerra n.d.).

In Brazil, there are a plethora of satellite-based forest monitoring systems, with NGO-led systems complementing government data. Key government systems include the Amazon Deforestation Monitoring Project PRODES dataset, providing annual data on forest cover and change, and DETER (Real-Time Deforestation Detection System) which provides daily/monthly data to detect deforestation and forest degradation (Rajao et al. 2017; May and Ozinga, 2021). Brazilian conservation non-profit Amazon's Deforestation Alert System (SAD) provides monthly reports on deforestation and forest degradation in the Amazon (Amazon 2019). While illegal deforestation cannot be detected from satellite imagery alone, the Mapbiomas Alerta Initiative validates and refines deforestation alerts by cross-referencing spatial information with other territorial information, including deforestation authorizations and protected area boundaries (MapBiomas 2025). Amazon has also worked

with Microsoft on artificial intelligence tool PrevisIA to predict areas of high deforestation risk (Ennes and Chaves 2021). Such data can support community monitoring of indigenous land. For example, in Acre state, a national NGO has trained Indigenous people in agroforestry and land management, including surveillance techniques to monitor threats of poaching, illegal logging and cattle grazing. Agents use drones and GPS to gather information, which is sent to the federal agency for Indigenous affairs (Ennes and Chaves 2021).

The NGO Rainforest Foundation US has supported indigenous monitors in Peru to monitor and report on deforestation in their territories by providing tools, training and satellite imagery (González and Kröger 2023). To overcome poor internet connection, satellite information is passed to regional data hubs, from which monitors can periodically download information to smartphones. Monitors can then investigate satellite-detected early deforestation alerts and decide whether to share with the community, NGOs or government institutions. Importantly, indigenous monitors played an active role in all phases of the project and data remains indigenous property, providing a transformative alternative to digital extractivism. This model has been successful in developing dialogue between communities and the Peruvian state to cooperate in combating deforestation, while retaining community autonomy and redressing imbalances of power and agency (González and Kröger 2023).

These examples illustrate how advances in earth observation technologies and publicly available platforms, together with bespoke tools and bottom-up approaches, can be revolutionary in enhancing the ability of independent monitors and IP and LCs to participate in deforestation monitoring activities and forest protection.

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Stakeholder Engagement Workshop in Yaoundé (Cameroon), October 2024. Credit: Tekeu Tessa Dominique.

6.9. INDUSTRY-WIDE AGREEMENTS: AN EXAMPLE FROM THE AMAZON

Industry-wide agreements are collective commitments among companies within the same sector to establish and enforce shared standards and practices. They aim to resolve coordination challenges and regulate market behaviour more effectively than individual actions. Their success depends on broad participation, clear monitoring and enforcement mechanisms, and the ability to exclude non-compliant actors. The Amazon Soy Moratorium (ASM) is a notable example, where major soybean traders agreed not to buy soy from areas deforested after July 2006. By leveraging market power, the ASM helped prevent the conversion of approximately 1.8 million hectares of forest between 2006 and 2016. However, such agreements face challenges, particularly leakage effects. Evidence suggests the ASM displaced agriculture from the Amazon to Brazil's Cerrado biome. Addressing leakage requires expanding agreements beyond specific regions, integrating with public environmental regulations, creating voluntary instruments that promote biodiversity protection beyond deforestation, and combining supply chain initiatives with broader landscape approaches.

6.9.1. COLLECTIVE COMMITMENTS FOR INDUSTRY-WIDE COORDINATION AND COMPLIANCE

Industry-wide agreements can be seen as collective commitments established among companies within the same industry to set and enforce common rules, standards, and practices (Lemos and Agrawal 2006). These commitments seek to overcome coordination problems, manage competition and regulate market behaviours more effectively than individual or unilateral company actions (Grabs et al. 2021a).

Agreements typically create mutual commitments between companies and verify and enforce compliance of the agreement,

through methods such as contracts, independent audits and penalties for companies that break the rules (Lambin et al. 2018). The effectiveness of agreements are underpinned by critical conditions such as widespread participation (ensuring high market coverage), the presence of clearly defined monitoring and enforcement mechanisms, and the ability to exclude non-compliant actors from the market, which compels adherence across the entire industry (Lambin and Furumo 2023). These arrangements often standardize industry practices, enhance transparency, facilitate collective bargaining and may provide market incentives such as preferential market access or price premiums for compliant participants.

Industry-wide agreements are needed because many environmental and social problems are concentrated in specific industries, requiring companies in those sectors to work together on solutions. Industry-wide agreements can mobilize collective action among major market actors (eg traders, processors and retailers) in these sectors. By collectively enforcing rigorous standards and excluding non-compliant products, these agreements directly address sector-specific issues at their source, achieving greater efficacy in managing industry-specific problems than isolated corporate actions could (Grabs et al. 2021a).

6.9.2. SCIENTIFIC AND EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE OF APPLICATION: THE AMAZON SOY MORATORIUM

The Amazon Soy Moratorium (ASM) in Brazil is an example of an industry-wide agreement that successfully targeted deforestation linked to soy production in the Amazon biome. The Moratorium was initiated in 2006 following intense non-governmental organization (NGO) advocacy, particularly a Greenpeace report that linked deforestation to soy used by major global fast-food chains. The ASM brought together traders, NGOs and later governmental actors. Major soybean traders associated with the Brazilian Association of Vegetable Oil Industries (ABIOVE) and the National Association of Cereal Exporters (ANEC) committed not to purchase soy from recently deforested areas after July 2006¹⁷.

¹⁷ Initially, the ASM prohibited the purchase of soybeans grown on lands cleared after 24 July 2006. The date later revised to 22 July 2008 to align with the 2012 revisions of Brazil's Forest Code.

The creation of the ASM was crucial due to widespread land conversion in the Amazon biome for agricultural production and soybean cultivation, which was considered the most profitable land use in that area (Nepstad et al. 2014). ASM was originally governed by non-state actors, including NGOs and agribusiness associations. Today, the monitoring and enforcement is overseen by the Soy Working Group, which is a multi-stakeholder dialogue that involves the Brazilian Government (Piatto 2016; Moratória da Soja n.d.). Using property-level information and satellite data, this working group produces an annual report that identifies farms with potential ASM violations, allowing soy traders to verify the compliance of potential suppliers (Moratória da Soja n.d.).

The ASM effectively reduced deforestation by leveraging the significant market power of its trader signatories, who collectively control a substantial share of the soy market. This market power enabled the traders to implement a market exclusion mechanism by refusing to purchase soy from farms that had been identified as non-compliant. This created a strong economic disincentive for deforestation-linked production. Empirical studies of the ASM demonstrate a substantial decline in soy-driven deforestation across the Brazilian Amazon. Between 2006 and 2016, the ASM reduced annual deforestation rates on soy-suitable lands by 0.66 per cent, sparing approximately 1.8 million hectares of forest from conversion (Heilmayr et al. 2020). Despite a 260 per cent increase in soy-planted area from 2006 onwards, soy cultivation within newly deforested areas remained exceptionally low at just over one per cent of the total soy area (Greenpeace 2025). Given these consistent outcomes, the ASM stands as an example of an industry-wide binding agreement that successfully aligned agricultural expansion with forest conservation goals.

Leakage effects in industry-wide agreements

Despite their advantages, industry-wide agreements also have shortcomings. While such agreements are comprehensive in their industry participation, they frequently target

one or a few specific environmental issues and often have limited scope regarding geographic coverage. For instance, agreements might focus on reducing deforestation within a particular area while overlooking potential displacement to other relevant natural ecosystems. These limited scopes create opportunities for unintended consequences that can potentially undermine their overall effectiveness.

The ASM example illustrates the challenges associated with industry-wide agreements. While the ASM significantly curtailed deforestation directly linked to soy cultivation within the Amazon biome, some studies have identified substantial leakage effects, particularly into Brazil's Cerrado biome (a vast biodiverse area of savannas, grassland and forest). Studies have documented how the ASM may have intensified existing conversion patterns in the Cerrado. For instance, Moffette and Gibbs (2021) observed that the Soy Moratorium led to countrywide agricultural displacement into the Cerrado, resulting in an increase of 850,000 ha in soy production and a rise of 11,000 ha in deforestation in this region. Similarly, Villoria et al. (2022) reported that around half of the potential conservation impact of the Soy Moratorium was nullified by cross-biome leakage, noting a 53 per cent increase in deforestation within Brazil, which offset half of the total 409,000 ha of avoided deforestation in the Amazon. Such leakage illustrates how policy framing can cause environmental harm by prioritizing one ecosystem at the potential expense of others¹⁸.

One potential solution to this leakage issue is to expand industry-wide agreements beyond specific regions to cover all activities by signatory companies, regardless of location. These agreements could require signatories to meet sustainability standards across their entire operations. Such comprehensive agreements would need strong monitoring systems, credible third-party verification and clear mechanisms for holding participants accountable. However, this approach faces feasibility challenges. Buyers would need to either block non-compliant goods or offer substantial premiums to cover the extra costs of meeting higher

¹⁸ It is worth noting that the Cerrado has been central to Brazil's agricultural expansion since the 1960-70s, with soy cultivation subsequently driving the loss of about half of its Cerrado's vegetation over the decades. This conversion has been more extensive than Amazon deforestation, with the Amazon representing the second phase of Brazil's agricultural frontier expansion (Rausch et al. 2019; Pires 2020; Schneider et al. 2021).

sustainability standards. For example, efforts to replicate the ASM approach in the Cerrado have faced challenges (Ziegert and Sotirov 2024). The Cerrado Manifesto, issued in 2017, and the following initiative, the Statement of Support (SoS), have encountered substantial industry resistance. Major agribusiness companies have expressed a preference for collaborative approaches with all stakeholders coming together through the Cerrado Working Group (GTC) (Cargill 2020). This illustrates the broader challenge that successful environmental agreements are often shaped by unique contextual conditions that may not easily transfer to other settings, even within the same country and industry.

Cross-industry leakage is another major challenge for industry-wide agreements. Even if one industry successfully reduces environmental impacts through binding agreements, another sector can easily step in to fill the gap, continuing deforestation or environmental damage. For example, land saved by reduced soy expansion might be used by maize or cattle producers instead, simply shifting the source of environmental pressures rather than eliminating them. To address this, it may be necessary to create coordinated agreements across multiple high-impact sectors at the same time. Aligning sustainability standards across industries could greatly reduce cross-industry leakage and ensure better protection of vulnerable ecosystems.

Such shortcomings are not unique to industry-wide agreements and may also apply to legislation. For example, [the European Union's Regulation on Deforestation-free Products](#) (EUDR) applies to forests based on the FAO definition¹⁹, but does not apply to other natural ecosystems such as the Cerrado. The EUDR also focuses on specific products from seven commodities (cattle, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, rubber, soya and wood). There is therefore the risk that EUDR leads to shifts in production to other ecosystems or other deforestation-linked commodities (leakage), rather than reducing EU-driven deforestation (Muradian et al. 2025).

In an effort to address such unintended impacts, the EUDR lays out a timeframe to review its product scope and potentially include other natural ecosystems. Hence, potential leakage may be addressed in the near future.

Furthermore, agreements that successfully reduce deforestation do not automatically deliver equal benefits for biodiversity. Biodiversity is complex and multifaceted (Cardinale et al. 2012), and it does not respond to forest changes linearly. As Börner et al. (2020) point out, conservation measures targeting specific biodiversity goals can show different results from overall forest cover trends. Simple assumptions like "less deforestation equals more biodiversity" can therefore lead to overestimating the environmental benefits of industry-wide agreements. Similarly, environmental gains may come at social costs, as demonstrated by criticisms of the impact of the soy expansion on Indigenous Peoples' land rights raised by NGOs (Ionova 2023). Addressing these shortcomings requires innovative approaches that enhance and complement existing industry-wide agreements. Potential innovations include:

- Integrating agreements with comprehensive public environmental regulations to provide broader geographic coverage and enforcement capabilities (Lambin et al. 2018).
- Developing voluntary instruments, such as biodiversity credits, that could incentivize producers to protect biodiversity beyond deforestation avoidance, offering economic rewards for conservation efforts that maintain or enhance ecosystem services (Wunder et al. 2025).
- Combining supply chain initiatives with landscape or jurisdictional approaches, fostering coordinated governance at broader spatial scales (Zu Ermgassen et al. 2024).

Therefore, a combination of regulatory, market-based and technological innovations will likely be essential to overcoming the inherent limitations of single-sector, geographically limited industry-wide agreements.

¹⁹ Article 2(4) of Regulation (EU) No 2023/1115 defines forest as "land spanning more than 0.5 hectares, with trees higher than 5 metres and a canopy cover of more than 10%, or trees able to reach those thresholds in situ, excluding land that is predominantly under agricultural or urban land use".

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6.10. SCALING FINANCE FOR NATURE WITH BLENDED FINANCE STRUCTURES

Blended finance structures fund initiatives with positive environmental and social impacts by using public or philanthropic capital to attract commercial investment. These structures reduce risk or enhance returns, aiming to deliver near-market-rate financial returns while advancing sustainable development goals. Scaling blended finance for nature-positive initiatives faces two major challenges: difficult risk-return profiles and high transaction costs. Many structures involve foreign exchange risk and political uncertainty. Nature-positive projects typically generate non-monetary benefits like biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services, which are hard to measure and value. Transactions often require lengthy due diligence and complex negotiations, driving up costs. Innovations are emerging to address these barriers. Standardizing processes and finance structures can simplify implementation. Improving transparency in data collection and impact reporting helps build trust and accountability. Adopting portfolio-level approaches allows risks to be aggregated and transactions streamlined, making blended finance more efficient and scalable for nature-positive outcomes

6.10.1. BLENDED FINANCE MECHANISMS FOR SUSTAINABLE COMMODITY PRODUCTION

Blended finance is a structuring approach whereby public or philanthropic capital is used to mobilize commercial capital towards initiatives that have positive environmental and social impacts (Flammer et al. 2024). In these transactions, public or philanthropic organizations generally provide concessional²⁰ and non-repayable finance to de-risk investments for commercial actors to encourage their participation. As a result, blended finance seeks to deliver near-market-rate financial returns for the private sector while delivering on sustainable development goals.

The theory of change for blended finance posits that public and philanthropic capital (referred to as catalytic capital) can create additional impact by crowding in²¹ commercial capital into initiatives that support environmental or social goals. Blended finance is deployed to encourage private investment in sectors where the risk-return profiles of investments are not yet attractive enough for private actors to invest in alone. Additionality provided through blended finance can be achieved in multiple ways (Brears 2022).

²⁰ Concessional finance refers to capital provided on terms more generous than market conditions. This may include below-market interest rates, longer repayment periods, or partial forgiveness of principal.

Blended finance structures are most commonly understood to bring “financial additionality”, where catalytic capital being deployed enables additional commercial finance to be mobilized in a way that would have not been possible otherwise. However, Brears (2022) also identifies other ways that blended finance can achieve additionality. Operational additionality is an improvement in the environmental or social practices of an initiative due to the deployment of catalytic capital. An initiative could also create systemic additionality if it triggers broader systemic change, for example by acting as a proof-of-concept for investment in a sector that was not previously appealing to commercial investors on their own.

Blended finance can be deployed through a wide variety of financial structures, with the catalytic capital de-risking commercial investments in a number of different ways (Sustainable Markets Initiative and Investor Leadership Network 2024). For example, loans can be offered at below-market rates, or with a longer tenor (repayment period) than purely commercial loans. These loans can be developed using credit-enhancing instruments such as guarantees²² and insurance. Grants can also be deployed to fund technical assistance facilities and assistance with transaction design (Sustainable Markets Initiative and Investor Leadership Network 2024; Convergence 2025). Tailored technical assistance and support for the design of the blended finance structure can incentivize additional co-benefits and improve the market and governance structures that underpin the initiative (Brears 2022; Flammer et al. 2025).

Several features of commodity supply chains are particularly relevant to the design of blended finance structures. First, the opportunity costs to producers of not deforesting or converting land for production is often high (Lee et al. 2011; Li et al. 2020; Grabs et al. 2021b; Wilcox et al. 2025). Special attention must therefore be paid to designing the financial structure so that the producer benefits from not deforesting or converting land. Second, commercial investors may associate commodity supply chains with high financial and operational risks (Rode et al. 2019). Benefits from investment, such as higher yields or improved resilience, can take time to materialize and are not guaranteed. Producers are often exposed to fluctuations in financial and operational conditions such as input costs, commodity prices and weather (United Nations Environment Programme 2023).

An example of a blended finance product being used to reduce commodity-driven deforestation is the Renova Pasto loan product offered by AGRI3 Fund, Rabobank, and IDH (UNEP-WCMC 2025)²³. This product combines a long tenor loan with technical assistance to farmers wishing to restore degraded pasture and cropland. The AGRI3 Fund provides a financial guarantee that de-risks the loans for the commercial capital provider Rabobank. Farmers who take out the loan commit to zero deforestation or conversion of natural vegetation on any land that they own or manage. The blended finance structure consequently provides benefits for all three parties: the public fund (AGRI3) secures a deforestation- and conversion-free commitment, the commercial bank secures a lower-risk loan and the farmer secures finance and technical assistance (UNEP-WCMC 2025).

²¹ Crowding in is the technical term for increases in deployment of commercial capital made possible by the deployment of catalytic capital.

²² A public or philanthropic investor provides a guarantee by committing to repay part of the investment to the commercial investor if the borrower defaults or a pre-specified risk materializes.

²³ See the Responsible Commodities Facility and the Mobilising Finance for Forests (MFF) programme for other examples.

6.10.2. BARRIERS AND POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS TO SCALING BLENDED FINANCE

Barriers to scaling blended finance

Despite its promise, blended finance has not always achieved the impact or scaled to the extent that its proponents had hoped (Lee 2025; Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025). Here, we focus on two major thematic barriers to scaling blended finance for nature and identify potential solutions to overcoming the barriers: risk-return profiles and transaction costs.

First, investments in nature and deforestation and conversion free (DCF) projects face significant challenges related to their risk-return profiles. Prominent issues include foreign exchange (FX) risk and political uncertainty (OECD 2025b). FX risk is particularly acute in developing markets where local currency volatility increases uncertainty for international investors. Additionally, non-monetary returns – such as biodiversity conservation or ecosystem services – often lack clear valuation methods, further complicating assessments of returns (Flammer et al. 2025). Uncertainty from gaps in knowledge and understanding around ecological outcomes, project performance and local contexts exacerbate these risks. This results in higher perceptions of risk and lower investor appetite.

Second, blended finance transactions typically incur high transaction costs, making them slow and difficult to replicate at scale (British International Investment and Boston Consulting Group 2025). Long lead times are a common issue, stemming from extended negotiation periods and complex due diligence processes. Consequently, each deal tends to require bespoke structures. This increases legal, administrative and analytical costs and limits scalability and investor participation.

In this section, we discuss potential innovations and actions for each of the four stages of the investment lifecycle: enabling environment (policy and market foundations), financial structuring, execution and monitoring and learning.

Enabling environment (policy and market foundations)

Scaling blended finance requires clear policy and governance foundations supported by strategic partnerships across institutions and sectors. In developed countries, blended finance could benefit from changes to risk-management processes in investors such as multilateral development banks (MDBs), insurance companies and pension funds (Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025; OECD 2025b). These institutions are often prevented or deterred from investing in nature-based initiatives by financial regulations such as credit rating thresholds and minimum capital requirements. These rules can be barriers at the institutional level to deploying finance in emerging market and developing economies (EMDEs) (Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025).

Additionally, staff in MDBs are incentivized to generate returns and maintain credit ratings, which can be at the expense of taking risks to seek non-monetary gains for nature (Lee 2025; Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025). Lee (2025) argues that MDBs should be empowered to accept below market financial returns for high-impact investments. Shifting to a portfolio-level approach, discussed in the next section, would help to smooth volatile returns for these high-impact investments. To mobilize private finance at scale while delivering societal goals, there is a need for development finance institutions to adopt a more ambitious approach to risk and a less ambitious approach to maximizing returns.

Developed countries and EMDEs can seek to increase the impact-focus and coordination of public funding generally, and the deployment of catalytic capital in blended finance structures specifically (Mazzucato and Rodrik 2023; Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025). Platforms like [SCALED](#) (Scaling Capital for Sustainable Development), which aim to speed up blended finance transactions, reduce transaction costs and improve coordination and governance for blended finance, are promising innovations at the public-private interface (SCALED 2025). EMDEs could be supported to develop cohesive and sustainable industrial strategies and investment platforms that direct and harmonize

investment. This would ensure that individual projects support broader policy objectives and are not siloed (Mazzucato and Rodrik 2023; Lee 2025; Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025).

Financial structuring and risk management

A lack of standardization in blended finance structures means that structures are often developed and negotiated individually. This results in long lead times and high transaction costs (British International Investment and Boston Consulting Group 2025). The situation can be improved by trying to coalesce around standard archetypes of deal structures (eg British International Investment and Boston Consulting Group 2025; SCALED 2025) and reserving bespoke negotiations for genuine innovations (OECD 2025b).

A second approach to reducing lead times and transaction costs is shifting to a portfolio model, where guarantees and concessions cover bundles of assets (Lee 2025; Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025). For example, IDB Invest recently structured a USD 1 billion securitized portfolio called [Scaling4Impact](#) to crowd in private capital to a portfolio of MDB assets. By pooling risks, these portfolios could offer less variability in returns than individual investments, while still providing benefits to nature in aggregate.

There is also scope for greater inclusion of local and regional commercial investors, who are often absent from blended finance negotiations (Convergence 2025). Local investors are more likely to have local knowledge and so be in a better position to quantify risk in projects (Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025). This contrasts with international institutional investors who, lacking context-specific knowledge, may resolve their uncertainty by assuming a worst-case risk profile for the investment (Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025). Furthermore, a significant source of risk in international financing can come from currency exposure; local investors who accept returns in the local currency would be shielded from currency risk.

Execution: platforms, partnerships, and scale

Partnerships can support transparency by building collaborative positive-sum networks that allow investors to learn from each other through familiar communication channels. Partnerships such as [Innovative Finance for the Amazon, Cerrado and Chaco](#) (IFACC), [Partnerships for Forests](#), and the [Partnership Platform for the Amazon](#) facilitate networking, collaboration and convergence on best practice so that blended finance mechanisms are not developed in silos. Platforms and partnerships can embed the solutions, developed and enabled in the other stages of the investment cycle, in the norms and procedures of the institution. The most important themes to put into practice are:

- standardizing processes and blended finance structures,
- enhancing transparency in collecting and reporting data and impact metrics, and
- adopting portfolio-level approaches to aggregate risks and streamline transactions.

Monitoring and learning: data transparency and standardized reporting

Both investors in blended finance structures and the implementors of the initiatives they invest in should seek to be as transparent as commercially possible (Convergence 2025; OECD 2025b). Public sharing of risk management frameworks, impact indicators and results, and data on the ratio of public to private funds mobilized would help contribute to greater transparency and comparability within the sector. Rigorous ex ante and ex post reporting on best practice indicators will help both with project selection and finance structuring (Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025). Resources like the [Land Use Finance Impact Hub](#) offer best practices for managing risks and measuring positive impacts arising from investment in sustainable land use.

Other important data that could be shared include data that inform due diligence, information about the impact criteria of catalytic capital, and information about projects that

are funded and seeking finance (Lee 2025; Mazzucato and Vieira de Sá 2025; OECD 2025b). These data allow public and private investors to find each other, assess the viability of finance structures, and reduce uncertainty to risk. Due diligence could inform credit ratings that help investors assess investment risk (Cantillon et al. 2025). For example, resources like the [Global Emerging Markets Risk Database](#) (GEMs) help its member MDBs and Development Finance Institutions to run high-level financial risk screenings using aggregated data anonymized from data submitted by members on credit rating-related events in EMDEs (GEMs 2024). This process allows data collection from prior transactions to inform due diligence and project selection in later transactions.

6.10.3. REFERENCES

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6.11. PAYMENTS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SERVICES

Payments for environmental services (PES) are payments made to landowners to change their land use or natural resource management. These payments may be made directly by people who stand to benefit (Private PES) or by the public sector on behalf of people who would benefit (Public PES). For example, people downstream may pay to benefit from cleaner water that a forest provides. Three prerequisite conditions for implementing PES schemes are that the fundamental economics make sense for both buyers and sellers of the environmental services, that buyers and sellers have the capacity to set up and maintain the scheme, and that landowners have land tenure and access rights to provide the services they are being paid for. Design features that help PES schemes be impactful include spatial targeting to keep costs low, tailoring payments to costs, payments for outcomes, not actions, and monitoring behaviour and sanctioning non-compliance.

6.11.1. EMERGENCE AND USE OF PAYMENTS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SERVICES

Direct, targeted economic incentives such as payments for environmental (or ecosystem) services (PES) are designed to help better align supply and demand for environmental services, such as watershed protection or forest carbon storage. They are defined as voluntary transaction agreements between service providers (eg forest landowners) and users (eg downstream consumers of clean drinking water), and are conditional on contractually stated rules of natural resource management (Wunder 2015). Notably, most PES are about contracts between a finite group of predefined parties, rather than real markets with multiple stakeholders in simultaneous demand and supply group action.

In contrast to value chain-based interventions such as certification schemes or, more recently, the EU Regulation on Deforestation-free

Products (EUDR), PES constitute an area-based approach. In this respect, PES are more comparable to traditional protected areas or Reduced Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation (REDD): certain agreed-upon resource-use restrictions are applied to designated land- or seascapes of environmental importance. Two different PES types are commonly distinguished (Wünscher et al. 2008):

- i. **Private PES:** These entail direct user payments from private service beneficiaries such as urban drinking water users or hydroelectric companies, and thus constitute an environmental finance tool.
- ii. **Public PES:** Public sector entities act on behalf of private beneficiaries in channeling conditional incentives to resource managers, compensating them for changing their behaviour.

PES schemes have, in some forms and under different labels, been around for several decades, but have evolved in scope and scale during this millennium. In Europe, the primary channel has been public agri-environmental schemes (eg for increasing on-farm biodiversity). Yet, some private and public PES and PES-like initiatives exist (eg through carbon offsets or the EU's Rural Development Programme support to landowners). Globally, PES have been used primarily to incentivize forest conservation, paying forest owners or users conditionally to deforest less. Many of these have been located in the Americas (North, South, Central). Watershed protection schemes have been the classic and most important case, followed by PES focused on vegetational carbon sinks (Salzman et al. 2018).

In the PES theory of change, service users (either public or private) make a contractual offer to local landowners and communities as an on-the-ground intervention. The expectation is that these landowners and communities would understand and accept this offer, then change their land use and natural resource management in the desired pro-environmental manner. For example, they might refrain from converting a natural forest into cropland. This accomplished change vis-à-vis a relevant

business-as-usual baseline would then provide additional environmental services, such as cleaner downstream water or enhanced biodiversity protection.

6.11.2. CONDITIONS FOR SUCCESSFUL DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF PES FOR GREATER IMPACT

So far, relatively few PES schemes have been rigorously evaluated for their impacts by comparing their outcomes to a baseline of what would likely have happened without them (Pattanayak et al. 2010; Ezzine-de-Blas et al. 2016; Wunder et al. 2020). However, this dearth of evidence is similar to other conservation instruments (Ferraro and Pattanayak 2006). Overall, PES appear satisfactorily impactful compared to other conservation instruments, but highly variable across different scrutinized initiatives and geographies (Wunder et al. 2020).

“Success” for a PES intervention can be conceptualized in two ways: emergence and impact.

PES emergence

The number of implemented PES schemes arguably lags what might have been expected, making them so far a “niche for privately owned land under conservation” and a supplement to public protected areas (Salzman et al. 2018). This is mainly because PES schemes require certain preconditions to be met to get up and running (Wunder 2013; Wunder et al. 2020):

- **Fundamental economics work reciprocally:** the willingness of service users to pay has to exceed the willingness of service providers to accept; if the demand-side payments offered are insufficient to cover supply-side incremental land management costs, voluntary deals will not be an attractive investment. It is important to offer payments that are large enough to shift the incentives landscape, both in private and public PES schemes: “pay enough, or don’t pay at all” (Gneezy and Rustichini 2000). This idea reflects behavioural evidence that

inadequate payments can crowd out intrinsic conservation motivations, making small payments counterproductive compared to no payment at all (Gneezy and Rustichini 2000). This creates a critical threshold effect that requires PES schemes to either meet meaningful compensation levels or risk undermining the very conservation behaviours they aim to incentivize.

- **Service buyer and seller institutions have capacity:** action may need to be collectively coordinated on both sides. In the case institutions do not already exist, actors would need to self-organize, including avoiding free-riding scenarios (e.g. service beneficiaries denying payment for their use).
- **Secure land tenure and access rights are granted:** only with these at hand can natural resource managers become effective service providers. Otherwise, third parties could jeopardize management, for example, by invading land or extracting resources. Governance systems to recognize tenure and access rights would need to engage with the complexity of legitimate claims over land, including the fact that many rural rights holders and Indigenous Peoples lack formal government recognition of their rights to lands, waters, territories, and resources (FAO 2022).

These three conditions provide practitioners with essential prerequisites for effective PES implementation: adequate payments, proper stakeholder organization and implementation of land-tenure reforms. When these preconditions cannot be sufficiently met, they serve as warning signs not to pursue PES schemes in order to avoid wasting resources on unviable negotiations.

Impactful design and implementation of PES

To design and implement PES interventions to achieve the best impacts, first and foremost on the environment, but when possible, also vis-à-vis socioeconomic objectives (such as equity and poverty alleviation), several factors stand out from the PES literature (e.g. Wunder et al. 2020):

- **Spatial targeting** is essential when limited budgets prevent large-scale enrolment. For example, rather than accepting all applicants, PES programs could prioritize landowners who can deliver the highest environmental impact at the lowest cost. Key selection criteria might include high service delivery potential, significant environmental threats and leverage for change or low implementation costs (Wünscher et al. 2008).
 - **Differentiating payments** based on actual costs rather than using flat rates per hectare, household or village can significantly improve cost efficiency when the costs of provision vary considerably across landowners and land managers. In the United States and Europe, differentiated payments have been more commonly accepted than in the Global South (Wunder et al. 2018). Inverse auctions take this further by having landowners compete to provide services at the lowest cost, at least partially revealing their true baseline costs and maximizing budget efficiency (Schilizzi and Latacz-Lohmann 2007).
 - **Paying for the desired environmental outcomes** (eg increased biodiversity) rather than actions (eg changes in forest management) can sometimes raise PES effectiveness (Reed et al. 2014). This can be achieved, for instance, by motivating contracted landowners to focus on results and apply their local knowledge in the process of achieving them. However, risk-averse farmers often reject result-based payment contracts when they feel the required outcomes are beyond their control, such as results affected by weather conditions or neighbouring farmers' actions (Thiermann et al. 2023). In turn, action-result hybrids schemes (ie paying for both) are frequently recommended as a way of sharing risks.
 - **Sanctioning provider non-compliance.** PES schemes require that compliance is monitored and violations are sanctioned to be effective. However, many schemes fail on both fronts. For example, most European agri-environmental programs do not systematically monitor compliance, and schemes that do monitor often never actually sanction non-compliant providers, even after years of operation (Wunder et al. 2018). Without proper monitoring and enforcement, PES schemes risk funding non-compliant actors and face moral hazard problems. Little is known about non-compliance rates in European PES schemes and tropical schemes are only marginally better documented.
- While these issues are fairly well-known in the PES literature, the proposed solutions, like spatial targeting, outcome-based payments, differentiated payments or reverse auctions, are only sparsely implemented in practice (Ezzine-de-Blas et al. 2016; Wunder et al. 2018). Hence, there is great potential for boosting future PES impacts by focusing efforts on aligning preconditions, improving design and enforcing contracts rigorously during implementation.

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Stakeholder Engagement Workshop in Yaoundé (Cameroon), October 2024.
Credit: Tekeu Tessa Dominique.

6.12. VERTICAL AND HORIZONTAL POLICY INTEGRATION

Policy integration (PI) is a cross-cutting implementation strategy to achieve outcomes with coherence and effectiveness, ensuring different policies are aligned, consistent, synergistic and mutually supportive. Integration can be done across sectors (horizontal-ly), levels of government (vertically) or areas of concern (thematically). Climate change, biodiversity loss and environmental issues are described as global wicked problems re-quiring joint understanding, decision and action. PI can prevent or mitigate negative environmental consequences by facilitating consideration of consequences in decision-making processes at earlier stages. Despite being a major sustainability principle for decades, PI faces challenges, including the need for sustained political will, difficulty in-tegrating laws from different sectors, lack of cross-sector coordination, and insufficient resources. However, opportunities for integrated implementation of biodiversity and climate targets exist through international agreements such as the UN Framework Con-vention on Climate Change and the Convention on Biological Diversity, and nationally through eg National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans.

6.12.1. COORDINATED POLICY FRAMEWORKS AND INTEGRATION CONCEPTS

This chapter provides an overview of coordinated policy frameworks and integration concepts, with a focus on vertical and horizontal approaches. It highlights key ideas and selected examples relevant to the challenges CLEVER addresses.

Policy integration (PI) is a cross-cutting implementation strategy to achieve an outcome with coherence and effectiveness. It is a process that ensures different policies are aligned, consistent, synergistic and mutually supportive. Integration can be done across

sectors (ie horizontally), levels of government (ie vertically) or areas of concern (ie thematically) (Nilsson et al. 2012).

PI's theory of change relies on the premise that integration can help avoid conflict, trade-offs, inefficiencies and implementation gaps between policies, and enhance the effectiveness of policies by aligning their goals, requirements and instruments. Its pathway of impact is to create win-win solutions in the making of cross-sectoral policy choices (Collier 1994). This is especially important when trying to tackle "global wicked problems".

Climate change, biodiversity loss and environmental issues in general have been described as global wicked problems. Finding solutions and best governance practices for these problems is difficult because their root causes are embedded in a complex web of ecosystems and societal, economic and political actions or inactions (Van Den Ende et al. 2023). Thus, tackling global wicked problems requires a joint understanding, decision and action that encompasses all the different pieces of the puzzle (Briassoulis 2004). PI can make it easier to prevent or mitigate negative environmental consequences of sector policy decisions by facilitating consideration of the consequences into the decision-making process at an earlier stage. This could also maximize positive environmental consequences (Persson 2004).

Given the governmental structures of work, such as the division of ministries and larger decentralization, policies tend to be created with a view to the specific interests and objectives of the relevant ministry (Jordan and Lenschow 2010). Policies are often created and implemented in isolation, without considering the goals and interests of other ministries and stakeholders. Policy coherence is another term commonly used to describe this process, while integration takes a step further to ensure policies are not only coherent but also blended and unified in their design and implementation (Briassoulis 2005; Nilsson et al. 2012). Other concepts and processes that work hand-in-hand with policy integration and in tackling

wicked problems include systems thinking, stakeholder engagement, adaptive governance, a whole-of-society approach, interdisciplinary collaboration and a long-term “futures thinking” perspective.

Applying PI depends on institutional (eg implementing organizational structures to coordinate different sectors and levels coherently), political (eg will and leadership that value the process) and cognitive (eg having frames of reference and external pressure) changes (Jordan and Lenschow 2010). Integration should be accounted for in a policy's full cycle, from formulation to implementation and evaluation. Many frameworks have been developed for PI.

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has been assisting countries to implement policy coherence for sustainable development for a long time. Figure 1 illustrates the OECD framework for achieving policy coherence in sustainable development, presenting eight interconnected building blocks. The diagram shows how different governance elements, from monitoring and political commitment to stakeholder engagement and policy integration, form an integrated approach to implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Each building block addresses a specific aspect of policy coherence. The circular interconnected design emphasizes that effective sustainable development requires more than individual policies (OECD 2019).

Figure 1. The OECD set of building blocks aims to bring policy coherence for sustainable development to governments with different political and administrative traditions.

The figure is reproduced from OECD (2019). *Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development 2019: Empowering People and Ensuring Inclusiveness and Equality*. OECD Publishing, Paris. doi: 10.1787/a90f851f-en. Copyright 2019 by OECD. Reprinted with permission.

6.12.2. FACTORS FOR SUCCESS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR INNOVATION

Environmental policy integration is not a new concept. Since the 1990s, following the 1987 Brundtland report, it has been identified

as a core principle guiding the transition to sustainability (Jordan and Lenschow 2010). Various governments worldwide have attempted to implement environmental PI in different scales. Box 2 presents some researched examples that can serve as inspiration and learning.

BOX 2 POLICY INTEGRATION STUDIES

Spain and Greece

Spain and Greece have incorporated long-term planning tools into their governance systems to enhance coherence in the formulation and implementation of policies.

Spain has the National Office of Foresight and Strategy, which analyzes empirical evidence of megatrends such as climate change, digitalization and demographic ageing. The office has a programme that aims to improve understanding of the social, economic and environmental challenges and opportunities that Spain will face in the coming decades, and to generate a shared vision of the country by organizing multi-stakeholder discussions.

Greece established the Special Secretariat for Strategic Foresight. It is tasked with identifying and exploring potential future challenges, trends, risks and opportunities for the country. Topics analyzed include the environment, energy, sustainable development, artificial intelligence and geopolitics. The premise is that by providing a shared evidence base on long-term challenges and fostering multi-stakeholder dialogue, these foresight processes create the common understanding necessary for coordinated policy responses across sectors.

Source: (OECD 2024c)

Sweden²⁴

Government measures that successfully increased horizontal, environmental PI:

- The Environmental Code: setting out general principles, directions and objectives, on which cross-sectoral environmental strategies need to build
- Sector responsibility: legal responsibility to all government agencies to consider environmental concerns and sustainable development in their actions
- National environmental quality objectives and sector environmental objectives with measurable and evaluated objectives
- Environmental management systems in government agencies: these follow a standard management cycle that includes environmental review, setting environmental policies and objectives, creating action programs, assigning responsibilities, monitoring progress, implementing improvements and revising policies based on environmental concerns.
- Green public procurement with a committee and an internet-based instrument to support public sector organizations with 'ecologically sustainable procurement'
- Environmental accounting: national research institutes working in monetary and physical environmental accounts
- Annual sustainable development reports
- National strategy for sustainable development

Source: (Persson 2004)

²⁴ Sweden in the early 2000s was considered a frontrunner in environmental policy integration, and the institutional measures documented by Persson (2004) were regarded as benchmarks for best practice by other countries and international organizations at the time. While much has changed in the two decades since, these initiatives remain instructive as early examples of cross-sectoral environmental governance.

Challenges

Despite being a major sustainability principle for decades, PI faces numerous challenges. These include the need for strong and sustained political will across changing governments, the difficulty of integrating laws developed for different sectors (often with conflicting terminology and objectives), lack of cross-sector coordination, insufficient resources and insufficient technical capacity (Jordan and Lenschow 2010; Nilsson and Persson 2017). In many Global South contexts, these issues are compounded by weak institutional frameworks, frequent policy discontinuities and pressure from external political economy factors (Jordan and Lenschow 2010; Nilsson and Persson 2017).

Research has shown that, at the European level, forest policy integration has served as a powerful rhetoric but it has been combined with only weak or vague policy initiatives throughout relevant sectors (Winkel and Sotirov 2016). Additionally, Sjöstedt and Kleinschmit (2016) identified, through a biofuel case in Sweden, that economic integration rhetoric is often stronger than sustainable integration rhetoric. However, this economic focus also creates an opportunity: if the business case for sustainable integration can be made clear and conclusive (eg through cost-benefit analysis), it provides a powerful avenue for impact.

Ylönen and Salmivaara (2021) found that a challenge in Finland is the lack of a common definition for sustainability, with policies placing more emphasis on “green technology” than on social sustainability. Climate-smart agriculture approaches, such as sustainable intensification and agroecology, can also be seen as examples of PI due to their shared goal of integrating climate change imperatives with agricultural productivity. However, research has shown that it can have unintended negative consequences, such as the exclusion of smallholder farmers in Kenya from the national decision-making process (Newell et al. 2018).

Opportunities for innovation

Regarding biodiversity conservation, special attention might be warranted for countries in the Global South with high biodiversity value, where rapid land-use change is likely to occur and where vulnerable populations are present (Alcamo et al. 2020). International agreements can be powerful tools for promoting policy integration at the national level. An example from Somorin et al. (2016) shows how Cameroon used REDD+ (an international forest conservation program) as a framework to integrate different policies nationally. Exploring synergies and integrated implementation opportunities of biodiversity and climate targets at the international level could help address cross-cutting problems and promote policy integration in national agendas (Pettorelli et al. 2021). This could happen through agreements like the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).

At the national level, an integrated approach to the implementation of National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs), National Adaptation Plans (NAPs) and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) could deliver efficiency and enhance synergies and co-benefits between climate and nature agendas while building policy coherence across sectors (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) et al. 2025).

One key takeaway learning from PI is that it is not a one-size-fits-all solution; the best way to implement PI is context-specific (Alcamo et al. 2020). Implementing PI innovatively at the national level might involve:

- Making sure the shared goal and definitions are clear to all sectors, and having a continuous exchange of information
- Having coordination structures at the strategic level, and not only through inter-ministerial working groups or liaison offices
- Ensuring a strong institutional system that can counteract political change, where PI outcomes can depend on political will and initiative

- Having conflict resolution mechanisms to arbitrate between inter-organizational differences when horizontal coordination cannot be resolved
- Making sure that, despite integrating policies, each policy has clear ownership and a decision-making procedure
- Having a framework and mechanisms to evaluate cross-sectoral environmental PI
- Having legal provisions and guidelines for stakeholder consultation, participation and transparency

- Making sure financing and budgets reflect PI goals
- Since wicked problems are always evolving, creating a governance system that is adaptive to change to reflect the current reality's needs

It requires a mindset change to see PI as a priority objective and not just a soft political goal, and to make it an everyday routine in implementation instruments throughout all levels of decision-making.

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7. CONCLUSIONS

The CLEVER Innovation Action Pool brings together input from a wide range of stakeholders invested in addressing the negative impacts of commodity trade on biodiversity and local people. It draws on a longlist of 58 strategies, innovations and instruments (Chapter 5) and discusses a selection of 12 approaches in a central repository for public and private sector decision makers (Chapter 6). It provides a range of innovations to enhance the sustainability of production and global trade. These innovations can be mutually reinforcing when selected based on understanding of local/national contexts and integrated into wider policy frameworks, maximizing the benefits to nature, biodiversity and people.

The innovative approaches highlighted not only represent actions for both public and private sectors, but also for supply and demand side jurisdictions. The solutions are context-dependent, with suitability and effectiveness depending on a range of factors. These factors include land tenure questions, production structure (large-scale vs. small-scale), industry structure in processing and trade (many small vs. a few large players), type of product (high-value vs. low-value, intermediate vs. final), market share concentration, institutional and regulatory environment and the wider political economy.

Stakeholder Engagement Workshop in Libreville (Gabon), October 2024.
Credit: Juan Manuel Vargas.

To aid a transformation towards just and sustainable trade and the protection of biodiversity, the approaches are recommended to be applied in a smart mix. A key theme that arose from stakeholder discussions and follow-up work was integration. Success will come from building on progress that has already been made and from collaboration among the public and private sectors, as well as among supply and demand actors. Power imbalances and structural inequity entrenched among these actors perpetuate biodiversity loss and need to be addressed. All solutions would benefit from safeguards to ensure that marginalized stakeholders are not left behind in implementation.

In the process of developing the CLEVER Innovation Action Pool through stakeholder co-design, one message rose to the surface above all. The innovation that stakeholders consistently request is inclusive governance. Innovation does not have to mean sidestepping existing momentum or entirely new activities. For less powerful stakeholders, being heard and in a position to input into governance mechanisms already in place would be a major shift from traditional, top-down policy. The lack of integration between policies at both sub-national and international levels is apparent, as are solutions and alternatives to address challenges. Therefore, in this context, innovation is less about complex reinvention and more about opening up existing systems to inclusive, participatory input, especially from stakeholders traditionally left out of decision-making.

Synthesizing the findings across the full body of work, key areas for structural adjustment emerge:

- 1. Complementing risk mitigation with positive incentives:** Most instruments nominated in the Innovation Action Pool emphasize asymmetric incentives that are required to make biodiversity-positive practices more profitable than conventional approaches. This includes balancing the ratio of requirements and economic incentives to provide more support for less powerful actors, such as smallholder farmers and forest owners, while requesting more support from larger and stronger players in the private sector.
- 2. Shifting from individual to collective and coordinated action:** Systematic movement from company-by-company voluntary initiatives toward sector-wide transformation was a tendency identified throughout the process. Sector-wide roundtables, binding industry agreements preventing agricultural expansion into forests, and coordinated biodiversity finance approaches are innovations that recognize that individual actors struggle to achieve systemic change within competitive markets that reward biodiversity destruction. Collective action is needed to raise the bar and move away from negative cycles wherein poverty drives environmental destruction and disconnected policies within and across jurisdictions cause leakage and dilute the forerunners of positive action.
- 3. From externality management to structural integration:** Rather than treating biodiversity as an external cost to be managed, instruments here seek to embed biodiversity protection into core business structures. Several examples represent fundamental shifts to how current mainstream economic systems operate. These include benefit corporations, community-owned enterprises that build environmental accountability into their legal structure and decision-making processes, granular environmental taxation that differentiates production practices and addressing power imbalances in producers by building their capacities to negotiate contracts.
- 4. The design and evaluation of policy and governance instruments should consider harmonization and coherence across different sectors and geographies.** Common themes for harmonization highlighted by stakeholders included:
 - Financial and regulatory convergence, where green financial instruments work in synergy with supply chain due diligence requirements and environmental taxation. These can enable coordinated stimuli from capital markets, regulatory frameworks and fiscal systems for the private sector.
 - Transparency and accountability loops, independent monitoring systems, public disclosure requirements and community participation mechanisms that can create mutually reinforcing accountability systems to overcome traditional enforcement limitations.
 - The need for local to global governance bridges, from community forest management, participatory policy development, and jurisdictional approaches that can connect local biodiversity stewardship with global market governance.
- 5. Success requires simultaneous and coordinated action across multiple areas.** Financial innovations with no regulatory backing (or blended finance for the state to de-risk) remain voluntary and small in scale. Regulatory requirements lacking financial and technical support may be unenforceable or leave behind smaller players.

Although this work initially centred on biodiversity, the stakeholder co-design process made clear that effective action cannot ignore the underlying political economy shaping supply chains.

(United Nations Development Programme 2021). Key issues, including land tenure, smallholder and community inclusion, corruption, transparency, state action, regulation and capacity building emerged as foundational (UN Environment Programme 2017; Convention on Biological Diversity 2022; FAO 2024; Convention on Biological Diversity 2025; United Nations Development Programme n.d.). These are not peripheral issues, but essential leverage points for any intervention aiming at real biodiversity gains. This work finds strong support for the idea that governance innovations for biodiversity are only viable if they address these systemic, interconnected challenges⁷, and if local perspectives are embedded at every stage of policy development and implementation (UNEP-WCMC 2021).

The added value of broad co-design was clear: it surfaced perspectives and solutions beyond any single sector's reach. This builds a strong case for future decision-making to adopt this open, participatory approach.

Looking ahead, CLEVER's Innovation Action Pool can work as a springboard for further research and dialogue.

Priority questions include how the various instruments interact, where harmonization across public, private and community initiatives is most needed, and which contextual factors strengthen or weaken linkages between supply- and demand-side measures. By mapping these connections, future work can pinpoint low-cost adjustments to existing mechanisms that offer the greatest biodiversity and equity gains. Staying true to the co-design ethos, this exploration would benefit from starting with local voices and proceeding to document lessons before wider application.

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Amazonas, Brazil.
Credit: PhotoSpirit
on Adobe Stock.

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